

Consumer engagement strategies guidelines

Guidelines on how to reach and retain end-users
in demand response mechanisms

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Consumer engagement strategies guidelines

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OTHER	Software, technical diagram, etc.	

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Executive summary

As the EU moves towards sustainable energy, co-creation is the future of the energy service market. In the context of continuously increasing and highly distributed renewable generation, grid operators require more flexibility from the grid, this entails a shift in the balance of power, turning customers into a new generation of collaborators and putting them at the heart of the energy sector.

The SENDER project is financed by the European Commission, under the H2020 programme, which aims to **develop and test** the next generation of energy service applications for proactive demand response (DR), home automation convenience, and security mechanisms. In this line, by engaging customers in a co-creation process, the project will shift DR from a reactive to a proactive approach.

To validate the elaborated use cases (energy solutions), defined by a Co-creation Steering Group (WP2), three demonstration sites will be implemented along WP7. The three involved regions represent different cultures and have a different socioeconomic context, this way providing a wide spectrum to facilitate the replication of the solutions after the end of the project. Therefore, **consumer engagement** is one of the main issues to be addressed to develop effective DR mechanisms, in this line the SENDER project will (1) procure consumers engagement all along the project lifecycle and beyond by making them participants of the co-creation process and the further design and development of project solutions and (2) will develop a set of consumer engagement strategies as guidelines for the project pilots to follow in order to successfully reach and retain consumers all along the implementation of the project.

These consumer engagement guidelines are based on existing literature review and on a socioeconomic and cultural analysis of the project pilots. For a better understanding, follow-up, and implementation of the strategies, they have been divided in **three phases**: recruitment, consumer response, and persistence.

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
CPP	Critical Peak Pricing
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
DR	Demand Response
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	European Commission
EE	Energy efficiency
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
FAQs	Frequently Asked Questions
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HVAC	Heating, ventilating and air conditioning
OTC	Over the counter (Bilateral contract)
PV	Photovoltaic
RE	Renewable Energy
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
TOU	Time of Use
TSO	Transmission System Operator
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1. Objectives

The main objective of this document is to present in a manner that is understandable and easy to follow, the path that the different project pilots need to follow for properly reaching, engaging, and retaining end-users into the DR mechanisms that will be tested (WP7). Therefore, a set of consumer engagement strategies are described, divided into three engagement phases: (1) Recruitment, (2) Consumer Response, and (3) Persistence. The strategies are presented in a practical way, tailored to each of the pilot regions' specificities.

Moreover, this document aims to showcase already existing strategies to engage consumers into DR mechanisms together with all the work that has been done to select the most effective ones, taking into consideration both the pilots' characteristics and the use cases to be implemented in each case. This will allow further interested parties to know how and where to start when defining successful engagement strategies to secure consumers' active participation and commitment into DR mechanisms.

Hence, to accomplish the expected outcomes of this document, the following activities were key:

- Analyse existing literature and initiatives on DR to identify available strategies to engage consumers into DR mechanisms.
- Have a better understanding of each pilot's context both from a socioeconomic and cultural perspective and from the relationship they have with the end-users and their potential reach in their region.
- Analyse and assemble the different characteristics to define the most efficient engagement strategies, a key aspect to the success of the project and directly linked with task 7.1 (WP7) with recruitment being the first engagement phase.
- Include NTNU's perspective on the choice of the selected strategies considering the segmentation done in T5.1.
- Have the project pilots support and validation of the different strategies' viability.

1.2. Use cases' description

Along WP2, five use cases have been defined to be tested in the different pilots. For the elaboration of this document, the already defined use cases have been taken into consideration since the selection of target groups will somehow depend on the chosen use case in each pilot and, therefore, the engagement strategies will need to be tailored accordingly.

SENDER aims to be a user-centred project, and therefore as a starting point of consumer engagement, a co-creation process was held to help define the project uses cases while ensuring (1) that customers become collaborators in the design of energy services and (2) that the uses cases are aligned with the needs, expectations, and concerns of the local population.

Table 1 shows a short definition of the five use cases presented in *D2.4: Use Cases Report* together with the key important findings to be considered when defining the engagement strategies.

Table 1: Use cases' definition and key findings

1st Use Case: Residential explicit Demand Response	
Short Definition:	This use case describes how the SENDER solution will extract flexibility from four different assets of a Smart Home (HVAC system, lighting system, hot water tank and Electric Vehicles (EV)) to propose them to participate in a flexibility market.
Objective (s):	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Propose/Offer Smart Home/Building flexibility to market actors through the form of flexibility forecasts 2. Adapt the behaviour of the Smart Home/Building following the reception of flexibility activation demands
Key finding (s):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-creation workshops showed high interest by end-users in Austria and Finland. End-users in Spain expressed interest if this use case enables participants to reject activation offers easily. • Assess regulatory feasibility according to GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) related aspects. • Even if the opt-out option is most of the time required by end-users who want to keep the control of their devices, it is important to note that it may endanger the proper implementation of the use case. It is important for grid operators to have the assurance of flexibility activation. If end-users regularly opt-out of DR schemes when grid stabilization is needed, grid operators will not be confident again to rely on residential flexibility to tackle their grid operation issues and won't rely on the SENDER solution anymore.
2nd Use Case: Maximize the use of Renewable Energy Sources	
Short Definition:	This use case describes how the SENDER solution will maximize the use of Renewable Energy to charge Electric Vehicles, heat domestic water and other domestic appliances.
Objective (s):	Maximize the use of the local renewable energy generation by synchronizing the operation of household's devices with period of local renewable energy generation.
Key finding (s):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-creation workshops showed high interest by end-users in Austria, Finland and Spain.
3rd Use Case: Minimize the electricity bill	
Short Definition:	This use case describes how the SENDER solution will synchronize the consumption of customers' appliances with the period of best prices from the energy supplier and/or distribution system operator to minimize the electricity bill of the consumer.
Objective (s):	Minimize the electricity bill of consumers owning a dynamic tariff contract by synchronizing the operation of household's devices with period of lowest prices from the energy supplier and/or distribution system operator.
Key finding (s):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finland: End-users clearly expressed their will to minimize their electricity bills, especially since more and more Finns opt for an Electric Vehicle. One mentioned that the benefits of such service might not be so high as the cost of electricity is already quite low in Finland. • Austria: This use case may not be applicable since there is no dynamic tariff in place. • Spain: This use case was the most appealing to end-users. • Essential to conduct an analysis to assess the economic benefits of the service in each country (T7.2, during the definition of KPIs)

4 th Use Case: Remote monitoring and control of household devices	
Short Definition:	This use case describes how the SENDER solution will allow consumers to remotely monitor and control some of their home devices (e.g., HVAC system and hot water tank).
Objective (s):	For Occupants of a Smart Home equipped with the SENDER solution: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allow consumers to remotely monitor their home devices (status, consumption data) • Allow consumers to remotely control their home devices (e.g., switch on/off)
Key finding (s):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most end-users expressed an interest in visualizing some energy and devices-related data in a dashboard. They would like to review their total energy consumption as well as device-specific energy consumption, energy generation if any, devices status and various sensing data (e.g., temperature, humidity) • Experienced partners expressed some concerns regarding the user-friendliness of some functions.
5 th Use Case: Peer-to-peer trading	
Short Definition:	This use case describes how the SENDER solution will propose peer-to-peer electricity trading to final end-users. The trading will be illustrated for all participants to overview who they sold/bought power (ID), the amount (kWh) and the cost (€).
Objective (s):	Peer-to-Peer electricity trading model makes renewable energy more accessible. The objectives are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making better use of distributed energy resources. • Increasing the share of renewables as end-users might increase RES investments to over more than their own consumption. • Empowering consumers by turning them from passive to active actors of the energy system. <p>The ambition of SENDER is also to illustrate peer-to-peer trading on long-term perspective to highlight the potential benefits for final end-users and maybe to push some regulation changes to allow it in more European countries.</p>
Key finding (s):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finland: Some end-users conveyed a strong preference for a “faceless network” as monetary relationships may endanger good-neighbourly relations. It is important to assess the anonymization of the transactions and consider the risk of deanonymization – possible by studying patterns. • Spain: While this use case is not legally permitted to date in Spain, participants evinced a consistent interest in taking up this use case. • Transition to national law has not started in most European countries.

It is worth noting that the SENDER project aims to have a sixth use case defined for the implementation phase, nevertheless, when this document was written, this last use case was still to be defined.

1.3. Relation with other tasks of the project

As stated in the previous section, the identification and selection of consumer engagement strategies has taken as a basis all work done in *WP2: Implementation of the co-creation process*, a WP highly related to consumer engagement, since by making end-users take part in the design of the use cases to be tested in later phases is the first step towards effective engagement.

Moreover, this deliverable has considered activities on *WP5: Consumers' patterns modelling*, in order to include consumer segmentation variables in a coherent way when designing the surveys that were shared with the pilots' potential users in order to have a better understanding of the socioeconomic, cultural, and behavioural context of each pilot region.

Finally, this deliverable is also remarkably related with *WP7: Demonstration phase*, since it will be the moment in which the defined engagement strategies will be implemented and validated, allowing to prove not only the effectiveness of DR mechanisms at residential level, but also to know better which strategies work best in a particular context.

1.4. Methodology

This deliverable was built by first collecting input from the different project partners from WP2 regarding the analysis of each of the pilots' context and the further definition of the use cases to be implemented and tested along WP7. Moreover, to learn about best practices from other related Horizon 2020 programmes, members of the SENDER consortium participated in the BRIDGE programme¹ on citizen engagements, where different strategies were shared, and the final report was iteratively consulted. Additionally, an interview was held with the University of Mannheim, partner of the RENergetic² project, and also part of BRIDGE. To continue, a deep literature review was conducted to take into consideration already existing initiatives, their lessons learnt, barriers identified, and to search for best practices.

As a second step, a qualitative analysis was done involving (1) interviews with consumer or marketing experts from each of the pilots and (2) the elaboration of user profiles in order to develop a better understanding of each pilot's capabilities in terms of communication channels, networks and engagement experience, as well as of the population they targeted. Further, (3) a survey was designed and shared aiming to reach the pilots' potential users and understand them better.

Building on the analysis of relevant literature, the best practices learnt from other Horizon 2020 programmes, and all the collected data, engagement strategies for DR mechanisms were developed with the aim of reaching households from diverse and different social groups in each pilot site. The methodology for elaborating generic and targeted engagement strategies is described in Section 3 of this document.

2. Literature on key drivers for engagement in DR

This section aims to highlight existing DR mechanisms and how to properly engage the end-users, to identify available consumer engagement strategies and select the ones that make a better match with both the pilot specificities and the use cases that will be implemented along WP7.

¹ BRIDGE Horizon 2020. (2022). Cooperation group of Smart Grid, Energy Storage, Islands and Digitalisation H2020 projects. Retrieved from <https://www.h2020-bridge.eu/>

² RENergetic. (2021). Horizon 2020 Project RENergetic: Community-empowered Sustainable Multi-VectorEnergy Islands. Retrieved from <http://www.renergetic.eu/>

The literature review starts making an insight into what DR is, which are the technical and legislative requirements for its implementation, and the existing typologies. Then it continues with a section dedicated to the key drivers of behavioural change from a sociological perspective, providing key insights that must be considered for a proper implementation of DR programmes. Finally, the last section provides an overview of best practices and barriers that have been identified both from a theoretical analysis and a more practical perspective.

2.1. Demand Response mechanisms

Demand Response (Ojea, 2019) is a **shift or reduction** of energy consumption in order to match a desired objective, such as, load and supply **harmonization** (IRENA, 2018), renewable energy sources optimization, reduced generation costs, between others (Balijepalli et al., 2011).

The energy market is making a **transition** towards distributed **renewable** generation, this demands for a **higher adaptability** (Zsiborács et al., 2019) of the consumption to the available supply. In fossil fuel-based energy models, supply loads are modified to match consumption loads, this leads to uneven consumption profiles, elevated prices, and higher carbon intensity (Scarlat et al., 2022) due to more polluting technologies going into the energy mix.

In this line, DR is a mechanism that allows end-users to shift and reduce their consumption loads in exchange for **economic benefits**, while benefiting the grid at the same time, making consumption meet the available supply. Nevertheless, for consumers to take part into DR mechanism/solutions, this requires (1) a certain degree of behavioural change from a social perspective and (2) a vast smart tool deployment from the technical side, in order to gain consumption flexibility at households' level.

2.1.1. Residential DR technical requirement and typology

As already stated, DR is a service that requires both a certain degree of consumer awareness and active involvement, and infrastructure deployment. Some differences exist depending on the DR typology, thus, in the case of **residential users**, the technical framework for DR should consider the following three categories.

A. Consumer infrastructure

The aim of **Residential DR** services is based on the accurate characterization of users' load profile and the identification of feasible load-shifting actions. The **smart meter** (Cetin et al., 2017) is thus a crucial technical component without which DR cannot be easily provided to end-users, this tool allows to properly characterise the consumption profile.

In principle, all electric appliances whose usage can be dimmed or moved to a different time slot, can contribute to the load-shifting potential of each household. However, those appliances with large peak loads or with little time dependency tend to be more attractive. As widely known, households' energy demands are primarily HVAC (Naef et al., 2019) related, these can have different forms, from electric heaters to refrigeration systems. This demand is then followed by lighting and other electric appliances.

Subsequently, as **electric heaters and HVAC** systems play a key role with the daily provision of thermal load it can be used in times of low prices and take advantage of the buildings' thermal inertia

(Pan et al., 2017) and other storage mechanisms. Some appliances such as DHW heaters, can easily be either turned on and off when commanded, whereas others such as centralised heating systems need a more complex management and control.

Another key aspect to consider, is the fact that **smart appliances**, such as thermostats or dimmable fridges, are starting to be more present in many households, these can easily match different appliances to certain load requirements and peak power distribution. Despite of this, and due to the fact that smart appliances are not yet a norm in every household, smart plugs (Zhai et al., 2018) or controllers can be a perfect substitute, which can cover a similar range of functionalities.

Lastly, as the energy sector evolves and goes toward the path of electrification, new loads such as mobility are being slowly shifted from fossil fuels to electricity, **electric vehicles** will therefore constitute a major consumption load in households. Many of these electric vehicles are already being deployed with **smart charging stations** which help shift load consumption to low peak-hours (Jin et al., 2013).

B. Prosumer infrastructure

Playing a new role in the energy market, prosumers can shift both its consumption and production profiles. Due to the time dependency of production, the ownership of renewable energy sources (RES) such as **solar PV** can make more attractive the participation in flexibility markets, and also play a role in the internal grid by maximising the **self-consumption** percentage. Similarly, **electric vehicles** can also play an important role as a generator, their storage capacity can help boost electricity **injection** (Clement-Nyns et al., 2011) into the grid at peak consumption hours. At the moment, neither of the systems is widely implemented, the infrastructure is not yet prepared and there is a need for **smart tools** which properly distribute consumption and generation loads.

C. Market and tariff framework

Currently, European markets have significantly adapted their national policies in order to promote a more stable and distributed consumption profile (Morell Dameto et al., 2020). Additionally, the ongoing transition to renewable energies demands for an even more seamlessly dynamic match between production and consumption loads. This is well illustrated by time discriminating regulations, which can help smooth consumption peaks, or avoid polluting technologies in the energy mix by maximising the renewable production use.

2.1.2. Flexibility market legislative framework

In the early 90s, the electricity market liberalization took place in many European regions, at first, most models were based on the Wholesale mechanism and legislated by the Directive 96/92/EC³, which aimed at a bigger competitiveness inside the electricity market.

Later, the Directive 2003/54/EC⁴ took a step further and clearly designated the different actors and their roles, the directive emphasized the differences between the Distribution (DSO), Transport (TSO) and Market Operator. These two directives were the basis for all **European electricity markets**.

³ Directive 96/92/EC. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A31996L0092>

⁴ Directive 2003/54/EC. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32003L0054>

More recently, the Directive (EU) 2019/944⁵ was approved and between the most relevant incorporations, a new actor was defined, the aggregator, which plays a key role in DR mechanisms.

Every European region has its own characteristics, but all **markets are based on the same principles**. The actors are clear, and the market is mainly divided in three main categories:

- The **Spot market**, in which the Euphemia algorithm matches bids and offers.
- The **long-term markets** in which forward energy markets and bilateral over the counter (OTC) contracts are acquired.
- The **Balancing markets**, responsible of ensuring that supply and demand match in real-time (Böckers et al., 2013).

The electricity market configuration of each State Members defines which services the aggregator can offer and the extent of monetary incentives that can be offered to residential end-users. The load-shifting potential of multiple end-users is collected by the DR service provider, commonly known as aggregator, which can then use the Spot market to optimize their participation in the different existing energy markets.

2.2. Theories of Behaviour: Drivers of Inertia and of Change

Technological innovations in the field of energy efficiency and sustainability can have an impact if they are adopted and used by mass society. To reach the mass market, new technological innovations must be perceived by users as contributing to their self-interest, but also as aligning with their motivations, priorities, and values.

While research addressing the interests and needs that are critical for diverse groups of users to participate in DR programmes is still limited, the numerous motivations that incentivise individuals to adopt various technological innovations are well-documented. As such, given the novelty of DR schemes, this body of research is a useful guide on which to build comprehensive engagement strategies. The remainder of this section summarises the **key intrinsic and extrinsic motivations** that can be mobilised as incentives or information campaigns to participate in the SENDER programme.

2.2.1. Inertia and Risk Aversion: Key Drivers of Domestic Energy Behaviour

In energy contracts, inertia and risk aversion prevail over rational self-interested cost-benefit analysis.

When it comes to assessing the potential mass market uptake of technological innovations, it is common to analyse users as making rational choices with the goal of improving their own material situation. Users are understood to be capable of weighting optimally expected costs and benefits and of collecting the necessary information to do so effectively (Rogers, 2002; Shogren, 2012).

Nonetheless, when it comes to energy innovations, consumer behaviour and choices have been found to differ from this understanding of decision-making. Energy contracts and services show a **low level of consumer involvement** or of 'shopping around' (Kaenzig et al., 2013). Indeed, numerous consumers do not apply sufficient effort to find and analyse information to choose the optimal

⁵ Directive (EU) 2019/944. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32019L0944>

strategy, what makes energy a commodity in which inertia, routines, and rules of thumb play a key role (Herbes & Friege, 2017).

Furthermore, extensive research in behavioural economics illuminates that people avoid making decisions that imply change when the consequences do not have known probabilities. As such, the **knowledge barrier** that many consumers experience in relation to energy contracting may affect individuals' willingness to adopt innovations (Rogers, 2002; Shogren, 2012).

2.2.2. Values, norms and perceived moral obligation

Environmental benefits, the wellbeing of others, and complying with social norms and morale are key drivers of innovation adoption, and especially so when significant short-term economic returns cannot be guaranteed.

When it comes to making individual or household decisions, numerous values beyond economic or material self-interest play a determinant role. Extensive research evinces that people also act according to values they hold individually, as well as on social norms of status and/or good citizenship (Sayer, 2007; Scott, 1977). Firstly, just as economic considerations, **values** affect how people rank options, and how they identify what constitutes the optimal outcome to be achieved.

Secondly, people may feel a sense of **moral obligation** or of social pressure to take specific actions. This occurs more strongly when individuals are aware of the negative consequences of not acting in a socially beneficial way, or when they believe they can do something to alleviate a collective problem (Huijts et al., 2012). As concerns technological innovations in energy, values will condition behaviour if one has knowledge about the problems at hand, and if he/she believes that technology adoption will actually mitigate these problems, or that better alternatives are accessible and affordable (ibid).

Indeed, various studies report that **environmental reasons** are stated by users as one of their main motivations to take up smart meters (Darby, 2006). What is more, consumers' willingness to pay for domestic technological innovations augments if they positively contribute to environmental sustainability.

Since values contribute to shaping behaviour, and especially so where pro-environmental actions are concerned, a meticulous study and understanding of the value systems of SENDER's target users will be key to design effective user-centric engagement strategies: it will pave the way for the communication campaign and the design of incentives to appeal to such value systems.

2.2.3. Early adopters and the late majority: different incentives

Early adopters and the late majority take up technological innovations because of different reasons: the first because of intrinsic motivations, and the latter because of extrinsic ones.

Consumers can be thought of as groups of 'adopters' who begin to use technological innovations in temporal sequence, depending on each group's characteristics and drivers (Rogers, 1962). The early market base of new technologies are **innovators** – those who are risk takers, not very cost-sensitive, and sincerely interested in new technologies –, and **early adopters** – a highly similar group but one which is a bit less technology-oriented, may have ideological reasons (e.g., environmental motivations)

to take up innovations, and usually aspire to be opinion leaders in their communities -. The potential late market base of new technologies is divided into **early majority**, **late majority** and **laggards** that are cost sensitive, value turnkey goods and services, and demand ease of use.

To become self-sustaining and widespread in society, new technologies must be adopted by the late mass market. Substantial adoption by the early market is considered to be critical for a potential scalation to the late market base (Nygren et al., 2015). To date, DR schemes can be regarded as being in an incipient early market phase in most European states, as they are remarkably unknown to broad segments of the European population (Kotilainen et al., 2017). Consequently, ensuring that the SENDER scheme is widely taken into use by the early market will be decisive to pave the way to a more generalised commercialisation of the programme.

Kotilainen et al. (2016) poses that the early and the late market are drawn to technology adoption because of different sets of motivations. **Innovators and early adopters are driven by intrinsic motivations**: reasons that derive from the topic or the technology in itself, and the will to invest oneself into something. Research has identified that in technological innovations the following intrinsic motivations have been decisive factors for adoption: interest in technology, competence feedback, obtaining new knowledge, the desire to express oneself, participating in challenges and satisfying curiosity (Agarwal & Karahanna, 2000; Reeve, 1989; Ryan et al., 2006; Yee, 2006).

By contrast, the **late market groups are more affected by extrinsic motivations** – that is, when an action is performed with the goal of reaching a specific outcome or an external reward -. Extrinsic motivations can range from financial incentives (e.g., tax reliefs, savings), comfort in the realisation of a necessary task, enhanced quality and security, social recognition of using specific sustainable energy technologies and opinion leadership to climatic conditions that imply a high energy need.

Therefore, appealing to intrinsic motivations will be more useful at the initial phase of the diffusion of an innovation, when the early market base can be mobilised for activities of testing, providing feedback, and of engaging peers through opinion leadership. The relative importance of extrinsic motivations will grow when the late market base is the target (Kotilainen et al., 2016).

Furthermore, studies show that extrinsic motivations function as stronger drivers for the late market base when these are recommended and endorsed by close, trusted, or valued contacts (Rogers, 1995; Ryan & Deci, 2000). It is worth noting that various studies show that external rewards, if perceived to be conditioning, can crowd out intrinsic motivations of the late market base (Frey, 1999). Nonetheless, if such incentives are understood as acknowledging, they crowd in and activate intrinsic motivations (ibid).

2.2.4. Trust and the perception of fairness

When customers know little about a technology, acceptance may mostly depend on trust in actors that are responsible for the technology, on the opinion of trusted contacts' or on the perception of the fairness of the technological solution.

When potential customers encounter a **knowledge barrier** to understand either the functioning, risks and benefits of a new technology, its contractual format, or the problem these intend to address, people lean on **perceptions of trust and/or fairness** (Midden & Huijts, 2009).

Subsequently, customers assess the reliability of innovations based on how trustworthy its producers, sponsors, and sellers are (Huijts et al., 2012). A study shows that roughly half of the UK's energy consumers do not seek for better deals. Nonetheless, there were indications that they would do so if switching among tariffs and providers entailed less perceived risks and was more convenient (Carmichael et al., 2018). While smart meters may help to mitigate the perceived risks of incurring large expenses over the long-term, SENDER pilots would also benefit from evaluating perceptions of trust surrounding the programme itself, and other beneficiaries such as grid operators. Additionally, people also reconsider their perceptions of the trustworthiness of new technologies according to the views of trusted contacts or of opinion leaders they recognise. As such, to **build synergies with local trusted actors** or multipliers in the fields of sustainable energy, public policy, and regulation, as well as civil society organisations, can play a significant role in **boosting the willingness to trust**, and hence to engage, in the SENDER programme.

Furthermore, **perception of fairness** in relation to the production and implementation of new technologies is also a relevant factor conditioning the willingness to adopt. This concerns how specific technologies are implemented (i.e., where, by whom, who benefits, who bears the main costs, the responsibilities and duties ascribed to different stakeholders), as well as the decision-making process (e.g., transparency, who participated) (Eriksson et al., 2006; Wolsink, 2005).

2.2.5. Intrahousehold energy culture

Household energy use is regulated by an internal domestic culture of energy: with its own norms, habits and practices of homemaking.

Households with similar demographic and technical characteristics can widely diverge in their energy consumption patterns. Anthropological and ethnographic data indicates that, in the domestic sphere, **energy consumption depends on each household's history and culture of using energy** to create 'cosiness', comfort and sense of home through space heating and lightning (Wilhite et al., 1996). That is, energy is used by households as a resource central to the creation of 'home'. Such practices of homemaking are not universal, but rather emerge as agreed norms, values and routines each household develops over time. These habits are key to assessing consumers' willingness to adopt new technologies and to change behaviour, as they are long-established, most people feel a strong sentiment of attachment and/or entitlement over them, and they are rarely challenged. As such, the incorporation of technological innovations and the changing of habits and routines must also be understood as a demand to adapt meaning, and as a negotiation of new ways to create 'home' (Aune, 2007; Lie & Sørensen, 1996).

In a qualitative field study addressing the reconfiguration of the energy culture of households around the uptake of smart monitors, Hargreaves (2010), illuminate that most households chose to use the meters because of four reasons. These included (1) environmental motivations, (2) a desire to have reliable information on their own energy expenditure, (3) financial savings – although there was a general sentiment of disappointment caused by their smallness -, and (4) an interest in the technology, which was especially related to its aesthetics: monitors were highly praised for their "appearance and their use of coloured graphics" (p.6114). The latter reason points to the relevance of evaluating that the **physical appearance of the SENDER Box** is pleasant and can benefit desires of comfort and cosiness.

2.2.6. Physical appearance of the SENDER Box

Cosy aesthetic appearance, a visible location in the space of the house, and the messages of new technologies are crucial factors to sustain the interest of users.

Hargreaves (2010) identified as **key factors to maintain the interest of users** in engaging with technological innovations the location of these, and the messages these communicate. In this study, users felt interested in consulting and using smart monitors when they could select a budget, and the monitor helped them check whether they would meet their target or not. Another booster of interest was the capacity of some smart meters to show the relative energy consumption of different appliances. Furthermore, users also affirmed that location in the house mattered: if they did not see it usually, they would not look for it, and eventually forget it. Finally, users would use and consult smart monitors if these defined consumption in terms of money, as other measures such as kilowatt hours (kWh) or carbon dioxide emissions were meaningless to most.

2.3. Best practices and barriers to Demand Response

This section aims to present the barriers and best practices identified in other DR initiatives that aimed to engage consumers. This input is essential for the definition of strong engagement strategies, taking into consideration what has already worked, what has not, and how to face existing challenges and barriers to bring DR closer to people's daily life and therefore securing their active participation in the long run.

2.3.1. Consumer preferences and motivations

Based on existing studies and results of proven initiatives on DR, it is important to consider different aspects when addressing consumer preferences and motivations including variations in the DR programmes, different recruitment options (opt-in and opt-out), contract length, type of benefits, type of flexibility services, tariffs, between others. In that line, this section will showcase how to use consumer preferences to obtain a positive perception and therefore guarantee a more active participation in DR programmes.

Opt-in and opt-out recruitment options

DR campaigns can be differentiated in opt-in, when participants join in a voluntary basis, and opt-out, when DR is introduced as the default option and users must unsubscribe to avoid participation. Opt-out campaigns tend to have higher participation but present a similar or lower aggregate response compared to opt-in. Indeed, it can be argued that of all opt-out participants the only active "event responders" (those who shift their loads when requested) are those who would have opted-in voluntarily if given the chance (Chase et al., 2017). The rest of users who neither have opted-out or started responding can be said to be "complacent" users, who tend to adopt a passive attitude and avoid changes in their consumption behaviour.

The dedication of more resources for face-to-face marketing strategies will result in higher opt-in recruitment rates (US DOE, 2014), these strategies consist mainly of door-to-door recruitment, organization of local events (meetings, workshops...), counting with the support of well-perceived and trusted local organizations, such as public authorities, and creating a sense of community.

It is worth noting that one of the most robust findings on consumer participation in DR is that recruitment based on consumers opting-out of a default TOU (Time of Use) offering successfully enrolls a far greater proportion of households than opt-in recruitment (Brattle Group/ UCL, 2017; Chase et al., 2017). A review looking across 4,000 studies of consumer attitudes to TOU tariffs and over 20 meta-studies of responsiveness on field trials of TOU tariffs estimated 20% enrolment in TOU under opt-in and 80% under opt-out (Brattle Group/UCL, 2017, p.22).

Providing additional information and automation

Some studies suggest that providing additional information (such as current pricing levels, current expenditure...) together with automation technology to participants results in higher response (Parrish et al., 2019).

Automation and storage systems might attract more inactive (“complacent”) customers or those who have no time to dedicate to plan their consumption. “Not having to think about it” can be a strong motivation for users willing to cease control of their appliances in exchange for easiness and little economic incentive. Since higher control is given to the DR provider and more accurate load-shifting forecasts can be made, automation also enables the design of lower flat-tariffs which shift the risk from the end-user to the DR provider.

Pricing should not go alone

Even though pricing can be an incentive, some studies show that pricing ratios work much better together with enabling technologies both for TOU pricing and for CPP (Critical Peak Pricing), having a greater impact in the later pricing option (Faruqui et al., 2013). Further, Christensen et al. (2020) illuminate that the variety of results that follow the deployment of price signals is substantially associated with each household’s history of energy use, practices of home-making and understanding of which energy uses and level of consumption equate to a comfortable domestic living standard.

Familiarity effect

Just like “lack of knowledge” in the energy sector or more concretely in DR can be a barrier to the implementation, familiarity of the concepts can trigger its adoption since people who already use smart appliances or dual tariff show higher participation and active response. The fact of counting with the initial attention and/or interest of some end-users required to define some strategies that are able to use this initial interest and make it grow to retain them along the whole programme and beyond.

Making use of the “ladder of acceptance” (Carmichael et al., 2018) concept can help promoting a better acceptance rate and long-term commitment and/or change of behaviour. The latter of acceptance consists of a step-by-step introduction of DR services, starting with low-complexity and low-risk tariffs to familiarize and moving gradually towards complex products/services. Most people are risk averse and do not really like changes, and even less if they do not see a direct benefit or if these changes might have a negative impact in their daily life (comfort, time required...)

Gamification

Gamification have provided positive results both for recruitment, active response, and behavioural change since (1) it inspires people to learn more quickly or to attain specific objectives, (2) when

developed through a platform, provides immediate feedback on performance, and (3) it fosters social interaction allowing people to get some level of social recognition. Gamification is also a good tool for users to keep track of their progress, motivating them to do better.

2.3.2. Main barriers and challenges

In general participation does not appear to be affected by demographics (age, gender, etc.), despite some studies suggest that potentially more flexible users may include those spending more time at home; households without dependents; and users with knowledge of and access to enabling technologies and/or alternative ways to obtain energy services (Parrish et al., 2020). Considering socioeconomic characteristics is essential for defining tailored engagement strategies that can address the specific motivations, needs, and expectations of the end-users.

In the contrary to the previous sections, this one, aims to highlight the main barriers and challenges that have been identified through both a literature and a more empirical perspective, in order to include them when defining strong and successful engagement strategies for the SENDER programme.

Perception of control loss

Even though automation can be an enabler to participation it can be a barrier since some participants may be concerned since it can be associated with a loss of control (Hall et al., 2016; Lopes et al., 2016). It is essential to give end-users the power to choose how and when automation takes place, including specific agreements on allowed control including limited duration, adequate notification of control, and the option to override.

Additionally, Wiekens et al. (2014) suggest that there may be some end-users who prefer automation over direct load control because it is perceived as allowing them to retain greater control. Finally, some trials in the US showcased that while end-users seem to prefer to have higher control at the beginning, they end up being more relaxed after gaining familiarity with the technology used allowing for a greater direct load control by their utility.

Rebound effect

The rebound effect refers to the well-known phenomenon that improving energy efficiency may save less energy than expected due to a rebound of energy use (Gillingham et al., 2015), meaning that if people perceive they are being more efficient in their energy consumption, they may increase their consumption per se. Rebound effect is mainly analysed from an economic perspective, nevertheless, it is necessary to consider it when talking about behavioural change and providing the right incentives.

Through DR programmes, the aim is to reduce the energy consumption in peak load hours by changing people's behaviour and one of the main goals is to boost the environmental benefits this behavioural change would generate. Therefore, it is key to provide the right incentives so people do not fall into rebound effect and end up consuming more than they would have otherwise. Efficiency makes an energy-consuming technology less expensive to use, so people use it more often (P. O'Connor, 2015).

Knowledge barriers

Some studies suggest that consumers have limited knowledge of DR and its potential benefits, being electricity a complex concept that turns out in a routine and passive purchase that is not modified unless consumers are actively dissatisfied (Parrish et al., 2019). This knowledge barrier can end up generating mistrust of the energy company motivations (AECOM, 2021) and who is actually taking advantage of DR programmes.

Mistrust is a barrier that can be present from the recruitment phase until the active response and persistence phases. This issue should be dealt from the very beginning by promoting by measures that enhance transparency around DR in general and direct load control (Parrish et al., 2020), including:

- Providing information on DR from independent sources.
- Communicating how different parties (end-users and energy companies) benefit from DR.
- Notifying users of any direct load control actions taken.
- Partnering with trusted local actors, including neighbours.
- Increasing transparency during the programme.
- Being available and addressing technical issues in a timely manner.

Additionally, studies show that complex programs hinder participation and consumers end up gradually losing their interest when they do not fully comprehend the programme, this is known as the “Response Fatigue”, which can be mitigated by providing data to end-users in a variety of formats allowing for social comparison, since social interaction have shown to have a higher impact over users’ behaviour than other facts such as price (Shekari et al., 2021).

Consider seasonality

Seasonality can affect both positively and negatively to DR, since it may be harder for participants to adapt the electric consumption in a country with harsh winters or hot summers, than for others with a mildest weather. In the case of severe weather conditions, people might prioritize their comfort, therefore, other type of incentives would be required.

Requirement of new technologies

The fact of needing to install new technologies has been identified as a crucial barrier to recruitment, on the one hand due to the costs that it implies, and which must be incurred by the end-user and on the other hand due to space requirement and the disruptions associated to the process (Bird, 2015; Hall et al., 2016). Even though, having to install new technologies can be a barrier to recruitment, having them can help end-user to have a more active participation and avoid dropping out since aspects as automation or direct load control have shown to have a positive impact over end-users by reducing complexity and/or effort of use.

In the case of the SENDER project, the installation of the main devices will be the responsibility of the consortium (see *SENDER - D3.4. Specifications of supervision package*). Nevertheless, it is worth remarking that some participants may not count with technology (e.g. smart plugs, smart bulbs) that facilitates the implementation of some use cases. Therefore, these participants may need to do a small investment to be able to do some actual DR and benefit from it.

3. Engagement strategies methodology

This deliverable serves as a **handbook** to consumer engagement for both SENDER and relatable DR programmes. It adopts a user-centric approach to engagement and will thus be a valuable resource to programmes planning to include users in the design of flexibility schemes. More precisely, this chapter introduces a methodology to elaborate engagement strategies for projects as far as they aspire to take into consideration the preferences, interests of users, as well as their knowledge over potential obstacles to long-term participation, in the final structure and content of schemes.

Social norms, values, and material conditions are all key factors that shape the behaviour, opinion, and decision-making of individuals in relation to their domestic energy consumption (Horne & Kennedy, 2017). A user-centric approach that places special importance on understanding these diverse and multiple values and behaviour patterns of users, presupposes that these are not universal, and that they require a careful examination. As such, these guidelines operate on the understanding that **profound contextual knowledge can boost effectiveness** and endurance by adapting schemes so that these, function jointly with existent social norms and institutions (Vatn, 2010; Muradian & Rival, 2012). Accordingly, the methodology employed to design engagement strategies seeks to collect this knowledge by means of a qualitative context-specific examination of these variables in each target population and does so in **four steps**.

First, it addresses the assessment of potential channels and multipliers that can be mobilised to **collect segmentation data** in each pilot site. Second, it details the various research methods deployed to construct a comprehensive overview of the **user typologies** relevant to the context of each pilot. Third, it introduces the procedures through which to **analyse jointly** the various kinds of data to construct meaningful locally informed user types. Finally, it outlines key considerations to elaborate engagement strategies based on the described user typology study.

Overall, this methodology proposes an exploratory segmentation study that pairs demographic factors with patterns of values, motivations and environmental attitudes exhibited by each identified user typology.

To do so, this approach relies on the use of **mixed research methods**: qualitative interviews, creative tasks (elaboration of user “personas”), and the collection and analysis of descriptive quantitative categorical data. The use of multiple methods enables an insightful triangulation of data, a property of special relevance to test analytical rigour where simple random sampling is not feasible.

3.1. Building user-centric context-specific engagement strategies

3.1.1. Step 1: Assessment and Mobilisation of Channels and Multipliers

To date, DR schemes are in an early development phase, and as such what they entail and the environmental and technical problems they address are unknown to many. The emerging character of DR programmes implies that research addressing user experience and preferences are only partially documented, and that studies evincing best practices for user engagement are few and non-exhaustive.

Consequently, it is crucial for new DR schemes such as the SENDER programme to develop a deep understanding of the potential interests, preferences, and barriers that different kinds of users may experience in each pilot context. As part of Task 3.2.1. interviews were conducted with each of the pilots in order to better understand their local context and specific characteristics, the target audience of the programme, and pilot’s expectations of the SENDER project to fulfil existing needs and overcoming existing barriers.

In these interviews, potential channels were identified for the collection of both demographic data and insights on the motivations and incentives that would boost user engagement; together with multipliers that could give visibility to the project or enhance its capacity to reach a broader range of users⁶. Based on the pilot’s previous experience in user engagement in European projects, the following channels and multipliers were identified as having a strong potential for communication campaigns, building trust, and to boost engagement in the recruitment and consumer response phases⁷.

Table 2: Potential channels and multipliers

Communication and outreach channels	Multipliers
Local newspapers	Public Administrations
Pilot social media channels: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn • Twitter • Webpage • Instagram 	Recognised local entities with a commitment to sustainability or energy efficiency
Pilot official data base of contact details of energy consumers	Social event and festivity organisers
Take away informative material (flyers, brochures)	Community centres: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Neighbourhood level • Centres for the leisure of the elderly
	Schools

3.1.2. Step 2: Collection of Empirical Data

The bulk of the empirical data utilised to inform engagement strategies is constituted by in-depth semi-structured interviews with sociology and marketing experts, target user profiling tasks, and survey data. These data have been collected in each of the pilot sites. The election of these methods followed three interlinked criteria. First, conformity with the time, budget, and data protection requirements of the SENDER programme. Second, their replicability in further Horizon 2020 projects, as well as other European projects. And third, the capacity to triangulate data effectively for the mitigation of weaknesses in the application of the different methods. The reminder of the section details the data collection procedure and rationale for each data type.

Semi-structured Interviews

⁶ For pilot specific information on the channels and multipliers identified for the purpose of collecting empirical data, see section 4.2.

⁷ For a more detailed explanation of each of the phases that user engagement will go through along the implementation of the programme, see section 5.

One in-depth semi-structured interview was conducted with marketing and sociology professionals with long-standing expertise in each of the three SENDER pilot sites. The interviewed experts were selected on the basis of their professional experience in marketing strategies, user engagement for European projects, and/or consumer behavioural change in residential energy policy preferably, and in the broader field of environmental sustainability enhancement otherwise. The purpose of these interviews was to gain key insights on the values, social norms, usual practices, and features of the collective imaginary that could play a role in fostering sustainable domestic behaviour change. They were also crucial to learn about the most successful engagement strategies applied in the pilot localities and the incentives on which these relied. Finally, these interviews enabled the examination of the most effective communication channels through which to engage different social segments.

To contact these experts, the SENDER programme made use of each pilot’s long-established networks in their respective sites. The wide public recognition each of the three pilots enjoys mitigated gate-keeper effects and enhanced the willingness to participate. All interviews lasted ninety minutes and were held as online videocalls through Microsoft Teams platform. Two of them were held in English and one in Catalan. For their conduction, an interview guideline, listing specific themes to be addressed, was used (see Annex 1).

Alongside the expert interviewees, a representative from each of the pilot entities participated in the sessions. Interviews were recorded, and the main insights were subsequently transcribed manually.

Table 3: List of expert interviewees

PILOT	EXPERT INTERVIEWEE
Otaniemi, Finland	Dr. Anu Seisto – Team Leader of Future Consumer Research at VTT
Alginet, Spain	Alma Solar – Leader of Research and Development Department of ADEE
Weiz, Austria	Bernadette Karner – Marketing and regional development expert at W.E.I.Z.

Target User Profiling

For the purpose of analysing and identifying the user typologies most likely to be interested in acquiring the SENDER Box, each pilot partner was requested to fill in a qualitative target user profiling sheet. Target User Profiles⁸ are a tool commonly used in marketing research to deepen the understanding of the various market customer segments of a given product or service, as well as how these segments will respond to different selling strategies and product adaptations (Hauser, 2007). In the case of the SENDER programme, and for analogous projects, target user profiles were intended to assist in understanding how the joint functioning and implications of the social norms, value systems and material conditions of users discussed in the interviews play out at the individual level. That is, how the average person of a given customer segment would think about trade-offs between their different values and interests regarding whether to participate, and under what conditions, in the SENDER programme. Shortly, they complement the broad sociological insights learnt in the interviews

⁸ AKA Customer Profiles.

with a more humanised and individualised understanding of customer experience and decision-making processes.

These sheets required a descriptive detail-rich lay-out of the three most likely individual participants in the SENDER programme. They requested information regarding demographic characteristics, living conditions, residential energy behaviour, narratives they would mobilise concerning the SENDER Box, best trigger message and engagement activities, among others (see Annex 2). The Target User Profiles were completed in English by each pilot partner, who were singled out as the best actors to do so within the consortium due to their profound knowledge of both the technical features of the SENDER Box and of the population and its manifold energy-related attitudes in their respective pilot sites.

Survey: Design and Circulation

A survey was designed and circulated to collect quantitative data on which to develop user typologies evincing the environmental attitudes exhibited by different social segments. The use of a survey was intended to provide data-backed estimations of how the most frequently displayed needs, and priorities in household adoption of energy efficiency measures and appliances are associated with demographic and socioeconomic variables. In this way, a segmentation study is matched with data on the environmental views and behaviour of the sample population, and hence offers an insightful basis on which to build segment-specific engagement strategies. Additionally, through the survey information on the existing knowledge about DR mechanisms and the perceived barriers to involvement in the provision of flexibility services is collected, which extensive literature identify as similarly important to actual barriers in shaping daily consumer behaviour (Hargreaves, 2010).

The survey was co-developed with the pilot partners, and included a mixture of demographic questions, as well as Likert scale, rating and multiple-choice questions addressing the subjective perception of collective environmental priorities, fairness in the distribution of responsibilities between citizens and governments, and the needs, motivations and incentives that would make them adopt energy-efficiency measures, provide flexibility services, and participate over the long-term in innovation programmes (see Annex 3). The criteria that the elaboration of the questions followed were (1) ease of completion by the user, (2) understandability also among the non-expert population, (3) statistical rigour.

The survey was translated to local languages (i.e., German, Catalan, the finish pilot used the English version) and circulated as an online Google Form by the pilot partners. Each pilot selected the dissemination channels that they deemed had either a wide reach or the capacity to access key social groups in their respective sites, while meeting the time and budgetary constraints of the project. As such, ADEE relied on their regular communication with their consumers, and thus reached them via direct email contact. W.E.I.Z. circulated the survey on social media platforms (i.e., Facebook) and via direct email contact to followers of the Innovation Centre and/or to previous participants to European projects. And as the Austrian pilot, VTT shared the survey through social media platforms (i.e., LinkedIn).

Overall, data was collected from **109 respondents** among the three pilots. The table below summarises key demographic characteristics of the sample population of each pilot site.

Table 4: Pilots' demographic characteristics

	ADEE	VTT	W.E.I.Z.
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<i>Sample size (N)</i>	64	27	18
Age Range (Years)			
<i>18 – 24</i>	0%	0%	5,6%
<i>25 – 34</i>	4,7%	55,6%	16,7%
<i>35 – 50</i>	32,8%	18,5%	44,4%
<i>51 – 64</i>	48,4%	25,9%	27,8%
<i>65 <</i>	14,1%	0%	5,6%
Gender			
<i>Female</i>	32,8%	11,1%	55,6%
<i>Male</i>	65,6%	88,9%	44,4%
<i>Other</i>	1,6%	0%	0%
Education Level			
<i>Obligatory Education</i>	9,4%	0%	5,6%
<i>High School Graduate</i>	14,1%	0%	5,6%
<i>Vocational Training</i>	26,6%	3,7%	38,9%
<i>Bachelor's degree</i>	35,9%	22,2%	11,1%
<i>Masters, PhD, DPhil</i>	12,5%	74,1%	38,9%
<i>Other</i>	1,6%	0%	0%
Ownership of Housing			
<i>Owner</i>	92%	77,8%	72,2%
<i>Renter</i>	8%	22,2%	27,8%

3.1.3. Step 3: Analysis and Construction of User Typologies

As previously mentioned, there are to date few studies addressing the user experience component of DR programmes, and even less concerning the context of the regions of SENDER's pilots. Being thus a significantly uncharted field, the most adequate approach to interpreting and analysing data is an exploratory study (Stebbins, 2001). That is, the analysis aims at deeply understanding the context, processes and key factors that affect households' willingness, needs and barriers to participate in DR in each pilot site.

Consequently, the results of the analysis do not provide proof for or against a given hypothesis, but instead offer a sound knowledge base on which to draw user typologies that show relevant internal coherence, and which will hence require targeted engagement strategies. As such, the analysis to identify user typologies follows three stages.

Qualitative Data Coding

Qualitative data coding implied a first thorough examination, with attention to detail, of the data from the expert interviews and the user profiles. Through this examination, recurrent themes presented in different words could be coded, and in a second examination, the relevant information of each theme was grouped. Themes concerned any factor, multiplier, incentive, contextual history or

narrative, and group-specific attitudes and circumstances that may affect willingness to participate in demand response⁹.

To check the consistency of the themes and their content, the interview and user profile data were jointly examined. This cross-analysis of the two sources of data also allowed to identify inconsistencies, which were then discussed with pilot partners and contrasted against relevant findings in literature¹⁰.

Survey data analysis

The collected survey data included demographic and socioeconomic variables, as well as the environmental values, needs and main incentives that would make respondents change behaviour in favour of energy efficiency and flexibility provision. As such, summary statistic measures (e.g., proportions, frequency tables), and statistical tests of independence between categorical variables (e.g., Pearson's chi-square tests) were used to evaluate the degree and probability of association between single or combined demographic factors and specific incentives, motivations or needs for engagement in the SENDER programme. The previous process of qualitative data coding and theme identification was also used to orient the search for potential associations between variables (Jansen, 2010).

Construction of User Typologies

Building on the coding of themes that are critical for engagement in DR schemes, and the exploration of patterns and associations between variables, the multiple demographic and socioeconomic attributes of users that evince relevant variation in values or willingness to change their energy behaviour are singled out. These attributes or combinations of attributes are proposed as potential user typologies.

Subsequently, the validity of these typologies was explored. First, the various survey respondents that would fall in each typology was compared with one another, to evaluate the internal homogeneity of the constructed group. This is essential, as individuals within a proposed typology must resemble each other for a typology to be useful for targeted engagement. Afterwards, the various typologies were also compared against each other, to make sure that heterogeneity between them made the construction of a given number of typologies necessary (Kluge, 2000). Finally, the validated typologies were described with as much detail as possible (see section 4.1).

3.1.4. Step 4: Designing engagement strategies for user typologies

To design engagement strategies for the constructed user typologies, this deliverable built on insights from interdisciplinary literature, documented best practices from previous European energy programmes, and the collected empirical data.

Literature from environmental and energy psychology, sociology and economics was consulted to identify the incentives, messages, material, and socioeconomic circumstances that affect the capacity

⁹ Some examples of themes that emerged were, to name a few, the prominence of certain multipliers in building trust, the relative relevance of economic savings, or the values that would compel different social groups to change domestic energy behaviours.

¹⁰ See Section 2 for a detailed explanation of the main conclusions evinced by empirical and theoretical studies of relevance to user engagement in demand response schemes.

and willingness to engage in innovation programmes and to change domestic energy behaviour of the constructed typologies (e.g., Allcott, 2011; Aune, 2007; Darby, 2006; Eriksson et al., 2006; Horne & Kennedy, 2017; Kotilainen et al., 2017).

Subsequently, best practices learnt from other European energy innovation projects were analysed and contrasted with findings from literature. To do so, partners contributed with tips, and suggestions for strategies. Furthermore, SENDER partners also attended and actively participated in the BRIDGE programme, which is aimed at developing a database of best practices for citizen engagement of numerous Horizon 2020 smart grid, energy storage, islands, and digitalisation programmes. Beyond making use of the many propositions compiled by the BRIDGE programme, members of the University of Mannheim, partners of the RENergetic project, were interviewed in order to validate the proposed user typologies, engagement strategies, and to collect and incorporate further expert feedback.

Finally, the construction of user typologies paved the way for the design of engagement strategies in the following way. Since the user typologies were developed on the basis of evincing data-backed internal consistency of shared features (i.e., socioeconomic profile, main motivations to adopt energy efficiency measures, environmental values), they function as a most useful guide for targeted engagement. That is, engagement strategies were elaborated to operate as incentives, or as calls to people's extant sense of moral obligation, that addressed specifically the main motivations to change energy behaviour of each user typology according to the results of the data analysis. Moreover, where socioeconomic characteristics united the individuals of each typology, these were analysed meticulously to develop a comprehensive understanding of the structural preferences, needs and constraints within which strategies would operate. For instance, since households with children were constructed as a user typology, to develop strategies that are compatible with children needs and schooling schedules emerged as a guiding principle for the engagement of this typology throughout the duration of the programme.

3.2. Limitations

It is worth stressing some limitations regarding the possibility to extrapolate findings from the analysis of the collected data, and their representativity. First, given that the programme agreement did not include any budget share for the task of data collection, the circulation of the survey suffered from several constraints. In the three cases it was shared through the outreach channels of each of the pilots, or of their officers. While in the case of ADEE the survey was sent via email to all the users of the energy retailer, VTT and W.E.I.Z. disseminated them by posting the survey in social media platforms. As such, the survey was mainly accessible to a range of individuals previously acquainted with the pilots. Consequently, this implies that the final sample of respondents over-represented early adopters, and people who are highly proactive in responding and providing feedback. Secondly, the number of non-respondents in any of the pilots, and especially in Weiz, was non-exhaustive and cannot be read as a representative sample of the social diversity of the pilots' sites.

However, the weaknesses of circulating this survey on its own were mitigated by the collection of other kinds of data. Through the expert interviews and the user profiling tasks the documentation of other social segments (e.g., the late market groups, or vulnerable households) that were underrepresented or omitted in survey data. As such, while these interviews did not cover all the range of expert professionals that could have contributed various perspectives and knowledge to the research, the triangulation of the different types of data provided a more comprehensive overview of

the variation within each pilot's population of interest. Overall, the process of data collection and analysis to develop engagement strategies was designed and must be read as an exploratory study: rather than confirming or rejecting hypothesis, it offers a broad-ranging and systematic description and understanding of a topic barely researched to date.

4. Pre-engagement actions and resources

Building on interviews, user profiles and survey data collected on each of the three pilot sites, this section introduces **tips and general orientations** for a segmented approach to engagement befitting the context of each pilot. Literature in the psychology of energy use shows that the most effective engagement strategies that motivate users to actively participate in the provision of various energy services are those that are based on **individualised social marketing approaches** (Steg, 2008). In these strategies, information and marketing campaigns are tailored to the needs, preferences, and contextual barriers of specific population segments, seeking also to adjust the product or service offered to consumers' interests (Allcott, 2011).

Accordingly, this section firstly details the common and pilot-specific user typologies constructed as explained in the previous section, and which correspond to a segmentation which is useful as far as engagement into DR in the three pilot sites is concerned. It subsequently expounds the main incentives that findings from data analysis indicate that can drive engagement in the SENDER programme in the pilot sites. It concludes by addressing key aspects for the development of an effective communication plan throughout the programme. All these activities are considered to be key pre-engagement actions, in what will be called *Phase 0 of engagement*.

4.1. User typologies

Building on survey, interviews, and user profiling data, the following **target profiles** were identified as the most likely profiles to be engaged in the SENDER programme over the long-term. It is worth noting that these different target profiles may require different engagement strategies.

4.1.1. General typologies

Innovators and Early adopters

As expounded in Section 2, 'innovators' and 'early adopter' are widely used terms to refer to the first groups of consumers who venture into using new technologies. They usually belong to medium and high-income groups and take risks. While innovators are genuinely interested in technological advances, early adopters may be more driven by ideological reasons and seek or enjoy opinion leadership in their community (Kotilainen et al., 2016).

Based on survey data, in the three pilot sites 'early adopters' share the following features:

- They display a high interest in technological innovation.
- They display a high interest in information on sustainable energy.

- They consider evidence on climate change to be utmost reliable.
- They all evince a strong level of environmental awareness.

In the case of both VTT and W.E.I.Z., early adopters are highly educated: on average they hold one or more university degrees.

Households with children

In the three pilot sites, data analysis indicates that households with children are the most likely or willing household unit to participate in the SENDER programme, in comparison to couples, one-person households or multiples adults living in cohabitation. In the pilots of ADEE and W.E.I.Z., households with children evinced highly homogeneous demands and preferences for sustained engagement in the SENDER programme¹¹.

In the VTT pilot, families with children also share some features and attitudes that make them a meaningful category for engagement. First, in the Finnish pilot area, households with children were the only category evincing a substantial association with the willingness to participate in the programme. Second, according to the survey, families on average expressed the intention to acquire either/both an EV or/and PV system in the coming five years. Third, households with children are more sensitive to price when it comes to deciding on a new electric appliance. Fourth, families are the household unit most associated with the ownership and inhabitation of detached houses.

Individuals or households aged over 65

According to the findings from data analysis, individuals or households aged over 65 constituted a relevant differentiated user typology because they, on average, had substantial purchasing power and conveyed different necessities for sustained engagement with residential technological innovations. Further, according to literature, this collective may have different digital skills, and may display patterns of use of new technologies of their own (Holgersson et al., 2019). As such, this age-based segment constitutes an insightful user typology. Nonetheless, for the purpose of engagement to the SENDER programme, and given the breadth of this age segment, this user typology is also defined and narrowed on the grounds of proactiveness and the explicit demonstration of interest on broad energy issues.

In the pilots of VTT and W.E.I.Z., the survey circulated through official workers' social media reached this age segment only residually. Therefore, alternative and/or non-digital methods of engagement need to be considered to engage this age segment.

Concerning ADEE, there was a significant expression of interest in participation by people over 65. Nonetheless, the needs and preferences that they conveyed for long-term engagement differed substantially from those of other groups. As such, while this population segment may not be reached through a generic information campaign, it could be recruited and included in the programme through targeted engagement.

Youth aged under 35

¹¹ The specific demands, preferences, and interests of households with children are integrated in the description of each engagement strategy they concern. For further detail, see section 5.

Age segments under 35 also exhibit similar preferences and requirements for engagement of the consumer response and persistence phases (see Section 5 for a better definition of these phases). Furthermore, on average, environmental reasons feature also as a stronger motivation to adopt domestic energy efficiency measures under this age threshold, in comparison to individuals aged above 35 in the three pilots.

From survey data, it was inferred that recruitment from this age segments may be difficult since the SENDER value proposition may not be sufficiently appealing to them at first glance. For instance, in the case of W.E.I.Z., survey respondents aged below 35 were on average not interested in participating in the programme.

Vulnerable Households

Vulnerable households are those who are at risk of becoming poor, or remaining so. Vulnerable households experience economic insecurity, be it because of sustained unemployment, or difficulty with accessing labour conditions that ensure stability, beyond minimum wage jobs. Vulnerability is usually defined in terms of its multidimensionality and dynamism: beyond conventional income measures, vulnerability is also created as a result of legal barriers to accessing the regulated job market or public services, disability, disease, poor housing conditions, deficient nutritional intake, and exposure to violence and pollution, among others (Gallardo, 2018). These multiple variables reduce resilience to external shocks and risk the fall into poverty of households.

Vulnerability also depends on contextual characteristics, and as such is usually evaluated against different standards. Overall, vulnerable households are more risk-averse, and often are not aware about, or do not actively seek access to all the support schemes available to them. For instance, no vulnerable household featured among the SENDER survey respondents. As such, and in accordance with the insights that emerged from the expert interviews, these households may not be easily reachable through online communication channels of the pilots and may have different needs and requirements to be met in order to participate.

While this user typology may not constitute an easy target for future commercialisation, their inclusion is relevant to enhance the **positive social impact** of the SENDER programme. And beyond contributing to social justice in the short term, it will also serve to assess potential venues to collaborate or recruit as beneficiaries this user typology, which may be in the interest of not-for-profit organisations, public bodies and, crucially, vulnerable households themselves.

4.1.2. Context-specific typologies

FINNISH PILOT (VTT): EV Owners

This profile is a subsegment of the ‘early adopter’ typology. Nonetheless, their ownership of an electric vehicle implies that certain interest and priorities regarding energy efficiency and automation may differ. In the pilot site, EV ownership is more prominent within the age range of 25 to 50 years, among those who own the houses in which they live, who have an individual net monthly income that falls between 2500€ and 4000€, among those who live in households with children, and among men.

To EV Owners, SENDER can be marketed as offering new services for EVs (i.e., scheduling, optimising energy usage). To communicate the benefits that the SENDER programme can offer in relation to EVs, it can be a useful strategy to get EV owners on board for the entire project.

SPANISH PILOT (ADEE): Women under 50

Studies demonstrate that, among households participating in innovation programmes involving smart meters, these would be mainly consulted by one member of the household (Hargreaves, 2010). As such, to keep households engaged, it is important for SENDER to ensure that multiple members within participant households are interested and can benefit from the SENDER Box. According to survey data, in the case of ADEE there appears to be gender-based differentiated attitudes towards the SENDER programme. 65,6% of survey respondents were males, which would indicate that men in Alginet exhibit a greater exposition to information or a larger awareness of energy-related innovation topics; and/or may be more proactive to give feedback and propose themselves to participate in the SENDER programme. Nonetheless, the proportion of women manifesting their interest in signing up for participation was significantly larger than that of men, and especially so among women aged under 50. Moreover, in Alginet (Spain) mitigating climate change and guidance to adopt more pro-environmental ways of living are also a slightly more effective incentive with which to engage women.

Therefore, in the pilot of Alginet it will be highly useful for engagement to target both genders, hence ensuring that multiple people within a household interact and feel involved with the SENDER Box. Specifically, ensuring that women are equally involved and actively sought out for recruitment can serve this purpose: it can avoid their omission, should they not be directly reached out to, or if their specific needs and interests are not included in the information campaign and in the design of the engagement strategies.

AUSTRIAN PILOT (W.E.I.Z.): Active Collaborators

The city and wider municipality of Weiz are highly specialised in the sector of innovation in energy efficiency and have therefore operated as pilot sites for numerous European projects in the field. As a result, data from the interview with the European programmes marketing expert for the region of Weiz indicated that the portrayal of engagement in **communication campaigns** is key. A significant segment of the population would seriously consider participation in an innovation programme if they were included as active collaborators, and not passive recipients of benefits, from whom data is extracted.

In communication campaigns, but also in the design of other engagement strategies as well as the provision and treatment of user feedback, to participate in the SENDER programme ought to be presented as a choice **to take part in the advancement of the collective goal of energy efficiency**, or even to 'work' in a well-purposed project as active responsible agents. Given the relatively high environmental awareness and acquaintance with innovation programmes of the population of Weiz, SENDER may recruit a substantial number of individuals willing to do their bit for the energy transition and to collaborate in research if the programme is described and implemented as placing high value on end-users as agents of knowledge. That is, if their feedback and pathways for participation are taken seriously and explicitly treated as necessary, which is also highly in line with SENDER's user-centred approach.

4.1.3 Incentives for general and targeted engagement

Studies of behaviour demonstrate that various motivations, interests, and beliefs operate simultaneously and shape individual's actions and choices (Dietz et al., 2005). This section details the most determinant **drivers and incentives of participation** that can be used in each pilot site for generic and targeted engagement. At the end of this section, a table matching information regarding the target segments, their main characteristics, and which are the best incentives to motivate their participation in the SENDER programme together with target-specific messages to reach them is included.

Energy savings and efficiency

According to survey data on the three pilots, across social groupings the most highly rated motivation to select an energy appliance or to adopt energy efficiency measures was energy savings, through efficient consumption. The capacity to reduce the amount of energy used to perform relevant domestic tasks is appealing as it implies both a **household-level economic benefit**, and an **environmental benefit** relevant to society as a whole. As concerns the VTT pilot, due to relevant events in Finnish history such as famines and war, to save money is a relevant topic in the Finnish culture, associated with social recognition (Huttunen & Autio, 2010).

Possible **messages** that would work fostering this specific incentive could be:

“Save energy and avoid any unnecessary monetary expenses”

Climate change mitigation

The environmental benefits of DR and flexibility services have been utilised in marketing and communication campaigns to motivate households to engage in flexibility provision. To mitigate climate change was the second main motivation that would make respondents from all social strata participate in the SENDER programme. However, it is worth remembering that pro-environmental preferences and values stated in surveys tend to be overestimated. Likewise, concerning domestic energy consumption, this motivation will frequently be a stronger driver of behaviour change for opinion leaders and risk-takers who belong to medium and high-income ranges (i.e., innovators and early adopters) (Simpson & Clifton, 2017). Further, as in most projects of innovation diffusion and testing, early adopters and the environmentally-conscious will be the most likely individuals to self-select as participants.

- In the VTT pilot, data from the expert interview and survey indicate that environmental awareness is notably high and widespread, and a feature incrementally gaining in importance in considerations of domestic energy consumption choices.
- As concerns the W.E.I.Z. pilot, it is based in Weiz: a city of 11.756 inhabitants which is renowned for being the Austrian urban centre most involved and specialised in the field of innovation for energy efficiency¹². As such, the population of the site is on average significantly informed on the topic of sustainable energy.

¹² Innovations Zentrum W.E.I.Z. (2022). EINBLICK IN DIE ENERGIEAGENTUR W.E.I.Z. Retrieved from <https://www.innovationszentrum-weiz.at/energieagentur>

- In the case of ADEE, survey data evinced that a sense of moral obligation to personally contribute to the curbing of climate change is more prominent among those holding a university degree. Moreover, to mitigate climate change seems to be a stronger motivation to implement energy efficiency measures among the population aged below 50, and even more so among women. Nonetheless, as based on the previous experience in projects of ADEE, it is expected that interest in technological innovation and environmental awareness will not be sufficiently widespread to ensure full rapid recruitment of all the necessary participants.

Possible **messages** that would work fostering this specific incentive could be:

"Your actions can contribute to saving the planet"

"It's our time to adapt for the planet"

Economic savings and low initial investment

When it comes to domestic decision-making concerning residential energy use, **economic expenditure** is a key consideration of any household. As such, making sure that it is well-understood by potential users that the installation and maintenance of the SENDER Box and the automation of energy consumption do not entail any significant upfront investment, or any short or long-term financial risk will be key for recruitment and to avoid drop-out.

Concurrently, an extensive qualitative study of smart meter innovation programme testers illuminated that, financial motivations become participants' main interest in participation if they have been promised substantial monetary savings (Hargreaves, 2010). In these cases, participants felt disappointed and disengaged from the programme as a result of the unmet expectations. Consequently, the SENDER programme should **not overemphasise rapid economic savings**, but rather its cutting of unnecessary expenditure and additionally its non-requirement of investment, or financial risk-taking. Overall, stressing that SENDER entails 'one less problem', since it minimises expenses and can mitigate energy poverty through efficient energy management, can be relevant for the engagement of harder to reach groups, such as the **elderly, youth under 35, and vulnerable households**.

As concerns the pilots of W.E.I.Z. and ADEE, the fact that such measures required a minimal economic investment featured among the strongest, most widespread motivations to adopt energy-efficient appliances or measures. In both cases, sensitivity to cost appeared to be highest among households with children and among women. In the Finnish pilot (VTT) this reason appeared somewhat less of a must, which posits that the discourse on energy savings, which implies a reduction in expenses in itself, may be sufficient.

Furthermore, **product durability** was a stated preference of numerous respondents across the three pilots. Consequently, to guarantee the product durability of the SENDER Box could be an additional trigger to foster recruitment, and to dissuade preoccupations over maintenance and repair costs.

Possible **messages** that would work fostering this specific incentive could be:

“Save more, invest less”

Ease of use and comfort

When the use of new appliances or changes in behaviour have environmental purposes, most respondents stated that **ease of use or implementation** would be a determinant factor affecting their decision to participate. As such, it should be made clear to potential users that participation in the programme ought **not to require neither much work, nor much time**.

At the same time, demands over behaviour change should be minimised and left to the user to take the final decision. Several studies evince that, substantial requirements of change in daily habits and routines are associated with slower rates of uptake and retention of technological innovations (Hargreaves, 2010). Moreover, the user typology of households with children ranks amongst those facing the most impediments to change energy behaviour if this implies a rearrangement in schedules. This user typology faces numerous obligations concerning work, schooling and care, and therefore they may consider participation mainly if this is portrayed as an opportunity to be more energy efficient, but without having to change their energy consumption patterns timewise.

Nonetheless, nudge theory suggests that when individuals perceive that they have **freedom to choose**, as opposed to accepting a static obligation, individual and collective environmental values and norms can become stronger incentives of behaviour change (Ölander & Thøgersen, 2014). That is, the individual at stake does not feel conspicuously conditioned or impelled by other actors to behave in a certain manner, and hence intrinsic motivations to adopt pro-environmental behaviour crowd in (see section 2 for further detail).

Furthermore, as it has been considered in the identification and selection of use cases and in the design of website and the SENDER App, to expand user comfort regarding their respective residential circumstances and the management of domestic energy consumption should guide both the elaboration of incentives, social benefits (see strategy COR06) and the messages that feature in the information campaign (relevant for the strategies REC01, REC02 and REC05). That is, throughout engagement it should be communicated that participating in the SENDER programme does not decrease comfort in exchange for energy efficiency, but rather that it can augment comfort. For instance, it can increase comfort by enabling users to remotely start the heating of their apartments before returning home; or by assisting EV owners in better managing the charging of the EV through scheduling the inside heating of an EV.

What is more, SENDER can substantially boost the **comfort and safety** of households, which is of especial importance for vulnerable households and individuals aged over 65. **Sensors** shall be installed at participants' homes, which will enable services of security (i.e. by detecting intruders, and sending fire warnings) and **assisted living** for the elderly, by noting the absence of movement, and notifying relatives or neighbours. Moreover, SENDER can contribute to the prevention of energy poverty and its impacts on health: it can enhance energy efficiency, which entails an optimisation of economic expenditure in energy, detect water or gas leakages, and programme house heating efficiently. Therefore, SENDER's contribution to a safe and healthy living, should also be clearly communicated to these user typologies to get them on board within the programme.

Possible **messages** that would work fostering this specific incentive could be:

"Small actions, big changes"

Gaining knowledge, participating in energy efficiency innovation, and advancing the smartness of homes

The SENDER programme is an opportunity to test and provide feedback on a programme of innovation regarding energy efficiency. It also offers the chance to have a more active form of managing one's own domestic energy consumption, to actively interact with the grid offering flexibility services, and to trade excess energy with peers. As SENDER unites the dissemination of learning material regarding energy efficiency, flexibility, DR, and the energy transition with active participation and testing, the programme is likely to appeal especially to early adopters, whom may be interested in becoming **beta testers** (see strategy PER02).

As extensively documented, individuals who behave as **early adopters** in relation to various technological innovations are driven by a desire to **attain or maintain opinion leadership**, and to bring change to their communities (Goldsmith & Flynn, 1992). As such, accompanying SENDER informative material - especially in events, activities or channels especially targeting early adopters- with the offer to 'be the first', 'be a leader', and 'be a beta tester' can be effective in recruiting innovators and early adopters. Furthermore, the SENDER Box will enable the integration of several smart home appliances and functions, and the possibility to do so will increase depending on the level of automation in the participant's home. Early adopters constitute a user typology that is on average highly likely to already possess numerous features of smart homes. As such, SENDER should also be presented to this user typology as an opportunity to make the most, interoperate, and jointly manage the smart appliances they own.

Crucially, as concerns the Austrian pilot (W.E.I.Z.) the new legal framework allowing for peer-to-peer energy trading could also be utilised in a marketing and incentives campaign. Its novelty and the fact that it is a new opportunity for the Austrian people could be utilised as a strategy that appeals to people's desire and perception of social pressure of not falling behind in technological innovation and/or being ignorant of relevant breakthroughs. In this manner, in the pilot of Weiz, the SENDER programme can be marketed as an already made and operative scheme to take part in this innovation.

Finally, it is common among numerous families to emphasise and invest in a good education of children (Hornby & Blackwell, 2018). DR through SENDER can also be proposed and communicated as a **family activity** through which to be informed and **learn together** about a key contemporary topic such as energy efficiency and sustainability.

Possible **messages** that would work fostering this specific incentive could be:

"Improve yourself"

"Energy affects us all, let's learn how to improve our use of it"

The next table summarises all information regarding the target segments, their main characteristics, incentives, and messages that may work better to reach them and foster their participation.

Table 5: Target segments incentives and messages

Target segment	Pilot	Main characteristics	Incentives	Target-specific Messages
Innovators and Early adopters	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medium and high-income • Risk takers • Interested in technological innovation • Seek leadership in their community • High environmental awareness 	<p>Climate Change mitigation</p> <p>Gaining knowledge and participating in energy efficiency</p>	<p><i>"Be the first one"</i></p> <p><i>"Become a referent in your neighbourhood"</i></p> <p><i>"Be a change maker"</i></p>
Households with children	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High willingness to participate in the programme • Interest in acquiring EV or PV systems in the five upcoming years • Price sensitive • Ownership and inhabitation of detached houses 	<p>Energy savings and efficiency</p> <p>Climate Change mitigation</p> <p>Ease of use and comfort</p> <p>Gaining knowledge and participating in energy efficiency</p>	<p><i>"Let's learn together"</i></p> <p><i>"Energy can be a family activity"</i></p>
Individuals or households aged over 65	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harder to reach through pilots' official social media need non-digital methods 	<p>Economic savings and low initial investment</p> <p>Ease of use and comfort</p>	<p><i>"Gain control of your energy expenses"</i></p>
Youth under 35	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High environmental awareness • Need an appealing value proposition to reach them 	<p>Energy savings and efficiency</p> <p>Climate Change mitigation</p> <p>Economic savings and low initial investment</p> <p>Ease of use and comfort</p>	<p><i>"Be part of the new wave towards flexibility"</i></p> <p><i>"Be a change maker"</i></p>
Vulnerable households	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic insecurity • Risk averse • Harder to reach through online communication channels 	<p>Energy savings and efficiency</p> <p>Economic savings and low initial investment</p> <p>Ease of use and comfort</p>	<p><i>"Good value for money"</i></p> <p><i>"Secure your energy expenses"</i></p>

EV Owners	VTT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Subsegment of "early adopters" Medium and high-income 	Climate Change mitigation Gaining knowledge and participating in energy efficiency	<i>"Be the first one"</i> <i>"Become a referent in your neighbourhood"</i> <i>"Be a change maker"</i>
Women under 50	ADEE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High environmental awareness Reaching these women can help recruiting households 	Energy savings and efficiency Climate Change mitigation Ease of use and comfort	<i>"Gain control of your energy expenses"</i> <i>"Be a change maker"</i>
Active Collaborators	WEIZ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High environmental awareness Willingness to participate in the creation of knowledge actively, in partnership 	Climate Change mitigation Gaining knowledge and participating in energy efficiency	<i>"Be a change maker"</i> <i>"Let's learn together"</i>

It is worth noting that the proposed messages are thought more as a general concept that should be transmitted rather than the exact wording or expression that should be used. Messages need to be adapted to the local linguistic characteristics of each of the pilot regions. These messages will be better defined along the elaboration on the Engagement Communication Plan proposed in the next section (section 4.2.) of this document.

4.2. Communication Plan

This section is focused on detailing the key aspects that should be considered and therefore included when preparing the communication plan to be used for consumer engagement purposes. This communication plan should be drafted as a pre-engagement activity by the project pilots with the support of both Ecoserveis and Euroquality, the consortium partners experts in consumer engagement and communication respectively.

4.2.1. Channels of communication and outreach

To identify or develop effective channels of communication and outreach with a wide audience and, crucially, with programme participants is indispensable for successful engagement throughout a project. Prior to the initiation of recruitment, the following **communication channels** will be established in each pilot site. The use of multiple of them will constitute in itself a strategy to enhance outreach and to reduce the risk of insufficient recruitment or the exclusive sampling of early adopters.

- Official social media accounts:** One or multiple official social media accounts of each of the pilots will, where possible, take the responsibility to engage in SENDER communication and dissemination activities throughout the duration of the programme. The table below summarises the initial proposal of the social media channels to be deployed. Information published through these channels must be updated and checked regularly.

Table 6: Communication channels in the project pilots

ADEE	VTT	WEIZ
Email	Website	Website
Facebook	LinkedIn	LinkedIn
LinkedIn		Cities App (possibility)
		YouTube
		E-Mail

- Contact of Reference:** Users should have the phone and/or email contact details of a person in charge of resolving user doubts and queries per project pilot. This person should be responsive, and rapid in managing responses to potential difficulties, errors and hindrances users may encounter. If possible, this contact person should handle in-person visits over questions and queries, as having a physical location with in-person customer services may enhance the trust and sense of security of participants. It is relevant that specific contact hours are communicated and respected. Additionally, project pilots are considering the use of community online groups such as Telegram, Facebook. This will be better defined in the following months, also considering the type of users that end up being engaged.
- FAQS document:** A FAQs section will be included in the project website and available at the multipliers' working space and events in a flyer format, so people can take it with them and think about it at home.
- Already-established channels of recruitment:** The Innovation Centre Weiz has participated in numerous programmes of the European Union. As such, the pilot is in possession of a list of past participants whom the centre has the right to contact to offer the possibility to participate in further projects. And as concerns ADEE, as a DSO and energy retailer this pilot will make use of its existent communication channels with its user base in the 13.100-habitant town of Alginet¹³.
- The SENDER Survey contact list:** The survey that was designed and circulated for the elaboration of this deliverable allowed respondents to optionally provide their contact details in case they wanted to be contacted for participation in the SENDER programme. The table below summarises the number of interested participants for whom each pilot collected email contact details through the survey.

Table 7: Contact list from the survey

ADEE	VTT	WEIZ
41	15	13

All previously stated channels will be complemented by the use of the SENDER project website and social media channels.

4.2.2. Multiplier stakeholders

¹³ Nomenclàtor de la Comunitat Valenciana. (2018). Alginet. Retrieved from https://nomenclator.gva.es/nomenclator/resultado_v.php?periodo=2018&cpro=46&cmun=031

To maximise the reach and effectiveness of engagement in all its phases, it is key to identify and liaise with relevant **local multipliers** to:

- 1) Disseminate information on demand response.
- 2) Offer to participate in the SENDER
- 3) Hold events in which information related to SENDER (e.g., flyers, brochures) and/or stands to sign in for the programme can be present.

Among the most useful **multipliers** to be mobilised to raise trust and boost interest in participation are public administration, and opinion leaders (Goldsmith & Flynn, 1992). The first effectively **raises trust** among the late market base and, especially, can mobilise existent trusted channels of communication with vulnerable households. Regarding individual and entity opinion leaders, they contribute to shaping the opinion and attitudes of people of whom they are close contacts (e.g., civil associations, key figures or institutions with an explicit or socially recognised commitment to sustainability). As such, where possible pilots will also explore the possibility of establishing partnerships with local multipliers. The section that follows details the local multipliers with whom pilots are considering liaising.

W.E.I.Z., Austria

- **Newspaper *Weiz Präsent*:** This local newspaper is widely read in the municipality of Weiz and is known and consulted by a broad range of the population. Innovation Centre Weiz has previously relied on *Weiz Präsent* for the dissemination of their research output, as well as for information and recruitment campaigns for numerous other projects. There are 10 editions per year, one every but expect in winter and summer time where 2 months are put together in a single edition in each case.
- **Subsidiary Energy Consulting Agency:** This agency is a subsidiary of Innovation Centre Weiz in which citizens can freely request energy assessment services.
- **Municipality of Weiz:** The municipality of Weiz is one of the main stakeholders of Innovation Centre Weiz. In the locality, the mayor communicates with the public very actively: it delivers at least one message per day. Liaising with the mayor for dissemination would be an effective way of reaching a wide audience and building trust.
- **Office for Environment and Mobility:** This stakeholder is renowned for its work on environmental sustainability, and would thus greatly contribute to communication activities, awareness-raising, and the building of trust.

VTT, Finland

The Finnish pilot will evaluate and explore potential partnerships with three types of multiplier stakeholders:

- **Housing companies:** in Finland, household are part of the so called “housing companies” which are the owners of the land where the building/houses are built. These housing companies have annual meeting and is a good place to share new initiatives and even organise some dissemination events to reach households.
- **DSOs & energy companies:** the Finish pilot has a good relationship with the energy agency Väre though which it is possible to reach a lot of end-users from the different cities that will be part of the project pilot.
- **Municipalities:** of each involved city in order to promote the idea at city level. The VTT pilot suggests that cities are very interested in becoming more sustainable, therefore counting with

the support of some municipalities from a dissemination perspective could help a lot reaching target users.

ADEE, Spain

- **Senior's Citizen Social Club:** The club is a space of frequent socialisation for pensioners, and people of an advanced age. Partnering with this social club would facilitate the engagement of the user typology aged over 65.
- **Local socially minded businesses:** The pilot will also seek to liaise and involve local businesses whose social goals align with those of SENDER in an information campaign.
- **Schools:** In previous projects the pilot has collaborated with schools in the town of Alginet for awareness-raising activities. ADEE may thus retake this collaboration to disseminate information regarding SENDER to children and their families, hence including them in the programme.

4.2.3. Dissemination materials with an educational purpose

As already stated, with the support of both Ecoserveis and Euroquality, each pilot should develop dissemination content with an educative purpose to raise awareness regarding the energy transition, energy efficiency, flexibility services, and DR. This material should be able to convey to the general public key definitions, main processes involved in, and the societal purpose of each of these topics. The inclusion of additional topics of relevance could also be explored.

This educative content should then be regularly disseminated in the pilot sites through the pilot partners or multipliers, to the purpose of introducing little by little complex concepts that are not fully known by broad segments of society. The idea is to make an “educational work” through **constant and long-term communication**, so when the actual engagement starts, people will already have heard of the main concepts expounded. There three project pilots coincide that dissemination **content** should be basically on:

- General information about the SENDER project and the specific use cases.
- What is required from the pilot participants, so to be always transparent and leaving the whole process very clear to them.
- Explaining what will be installed how the installation process will be.
- Explaining DR and other energy topics from a non-technical perspective (energy literacy)
- Providing energy tips to end-users

The **formats** of presenting such education materials could vary between:

- SENDER marketing video as a first glimpse of the project.
- Short videos, such as TED Talks (including more content), Instagram (more graphic), among others.
- Local newspaper articles.
- Social media posts including infographics.
- Printed materials, such as flyers, brochures, posters to be available in public places. Some of these materials could be used also in a digital format.

It is important for all materials to be carefully assessed, making sure that the same message is being shared across the pilots, ensuring a proper communication of the project, its objectives, and the programme per se. Therefore, **common definitions** should be agreed in advance by both the technical and pilot partners, considering the availability of communication channels, the possible multipliers, and the target audiences. Additionally, to guarantee a higher visibility and success rate of the communication and engagement strategies, **keywords** should be defined for the different pilots.

Finally, regarding **timing**, since it is expected to be a couple of months between the moment people are engaged and the moment the piloting phase starts, due to the installation time, pilots suggest that it is crucial that communication is constant, either weekly or biweekly so people do not lose their motivation and keep engaged. For a wide and general perspective, a 1st draft for the chronology to develop such educative contents is introduced in Section 7, which will be better detail in the upcoming months.

5. Engagement and retention strategies

This section aims to describe the different engagement strategies that have been selected based on studies on residential engagement into DR programmes that are usually presented as encompassing three main phases, all of each are relevant for a programme's success: **recruitment, demand or consumer response**, and **persistence** (Carmichael, 2018). Addressing each phase meticulously reduces risks such as, not recruiting enough participants, not doing so from very limited social or economic strata, and to avoid drop-out in later stages.

Each of the three phases represents a time period in the programme, with specific objectives to be attained, and with multiple steps to be accomplished throughout. The division of engagement into temporal phases is useful to accurately order engagement strategies and to provide a more coherent understanding of when the implementation of a given strategy makes sense and can be effective. Figure 1 shows how the three engagement phases coexist through the whole engagement process.

Figure 1: Engagement phase over time

Moreover, a deeper description of each of the phases together with the actions that are encompassed in each of them is included below.

Phase 1: Recruitment

Recruitment, the first phase of engagement, encompasses all the moments in which a potential user is exposed to information relevant to participation in the SENDER programme, to the moment in which he/she registers. This ranges from learning about the existence of the project in general, but

also about flexibility services and DR, to assisting at events or webinars in which the details of the programme are presented. It also includes obtaining an individualised assessment of how the programme would work for their personal houses, and to choosing the most convenient method of registration.

Figure 2: Recruitment phase scope

Phase 2: Consumer Response

In the Consumer Response phase, strategies will be directed at initiating and consolidating behaviour change in terms of energy usage and response to flexibility activation demands. This phase would start with the user’s own acts of planning and reflecting how best to re-arrange its domestic energy use practices, as well as with the installation of the SENDER Box at all user’s residences. This phase would finalise when behaviour change is relevant enough for the effective implementation of the selected use cases, and once the required behaviour change is well-understood by the user, who is able to implement it without further relevant doubts and hesitations.

Figure 3: Consumer Response phase scope

Phase 3: Persistence

In the third phase (i.e., Persistence), engagement strategies will seek to sustain interest in the individual, household, and collective benefits of participating in the SENDER Programme. By extending interest and interaction over time, these strategies aim to accompany the user in the accommodation of behaviour change into his/her daily habits and routines. The ultimate goal of this phase is to ensure that the usage of the SENDER Box is both sufficiently interesting and comfortable for users that they may be willing to maintain their behaviour changes and uses of the SENDER Box once the programme is terminated or even be willing to go further into DR related actions.

Figure 4: Persistence phase scope

Since the aim of each of the engagement phases is different, the type of strategy to be used, the message to be sent, the correct timing of implementation (specific moment and duration), between other critical aspects will need to be adapted to the specific characteristics of both the implementation region and the concrete target users. Since this document aims to facilitate the engagement process of end-users into the SENDER programme, a set of engagement strategies, divided into the above-mentioned phases, are presented in a fact-sheet format, including all relevant information to take into consideration when applying them. Additionally, each strategy has an identification code, for a better recognition in further sections of the document.

It is worth noting that the “time period” and “duration” categories have been calculated on the one hand, by taking into consideration the SENDER project timeline from M18 onwards and, on the other hand, based on the experience of both Ecoserveis and the interviewed experts. These categories are recommendations which can easily be adapted according to the necessities of each of the pilots.

After the description of all the different strategies within each engagement phase, a table summarizing the key concepts is included for an easier selection of the strategies to be used by the project pilots in the moment of implementation.

5.1. Phase 1: Recruitment

Figure 5: Recruitment strategies

5.1.1. Information campaign

5.1.1.1. Dissemination of informative material in partnership with multipliers

Code: REC01

Pilot: All

Time period: Entire engagement process (transversal)

Duration: N/A

Target Group: General public; see Variations for households with children, the hard to reach (i.e., the elderly), early adopters, and for the W.E.I.Z. and VTT pilots.

Resources: Informative materials, both digital and printed (printed materials may have an additional cost, it needs to be checked with WP9)

Staff: The pilot team and a local communication and dissemination official if possible. Support from ECO and EQY for the elaboration of materials.

Purpose: Exposing various segments of the population of the pilot sites to information on the SENDER programme and on DR that is both accessible and meaningful to the general public. To this purpose, pilots will use **their own established channels** to reach the broad audience and will seek to **partner with key multipliers** to disseminate this informative material.

Engagement strategy and main actions:

1. Phase 0 (starting in April)

Together with the support of ECO and EQY, the project pilots will develop a communication plan to inform the population all along the project (see Section 4). This communication plan will detail the content pilots want to share, how they want to share it (format), when they want to share it, and where (physical spaces or digital platforms). When detailing the communication plan, the necessary resources for the different options will be considered. Finally, a stakeholders mapping will be done for the identification of potential multiplier to contact in further steps.

It is worth noting that the communication plan, will be adapted if considered necessary along the implementation process.

2. Elaboration and sharing material (from May onwards)

Following what was described in the communication plan (Phase 0) all necessary dissemination materials will be developed, both printed and digital versions. Before sharing materials, project pilots will start contacting potential multipliers both for having the possibility to share dissemination material at their venues and for the organisation of events (REC02) and other engagement strategies. The produced materials will be shared as it was planned in the communication plan:

- Informative **flyers and brochures** will be available in the pilot's own physical venues, in the multipliers' venues that accepted collaborating with the SENDER programme, and in events.
- **Posters** summarising the key insights of SENDER and DR should also be placed in publicly available outdoor spaces for information dissemination.
- Periodically, through pilots' and multipliers **social media channels**. The periodisation of social media posts will be key to sustain interest and to inform potential users more extensively, as it offers the opportunity to disseminate a larger amount of content divided over time.

Variations:

- **Monthly articles in newspapers** regarding DR: For the pilots whom in Phase 0 have identified potential partnerships with printed media outlets that are read by the general public or by the elderly, articles could be prepared to be disseminated through these channels.
- In the case of VTT and W.E.I.Z., pilots could also rely on their own specialised **newsletter** publication to reach innovators and early adopters.
- Communication by the **public administration**: In some pilots, such as W.E.I.Z, municipal administrations constitute key stakeholders. As such, W.E.I.Z, and potentially ADEE and VTT, will explore the possibility to partner with the mayor or any relevant authority to disseminate information in a trusted and widely accessible manner. In the case of VTT, municipalities are considered as key multiplier that can be crucial for reaching a higher number of people in the involved cities.

Effective Combination of strategies: This strategy can be combined with all engagement strategies and can be considered as a transversal strategy. That is, it can be applied all along the different engagement phases.

Highlights:

- Use an easy and understandable language, the energy topic is not very attractive to the general population since it is perceived as something hard to understand.
- As a start, the pilot of Weiz considers that information shared should pursue just a recruitment purpose but a more educational one, so people can better understand the programme and then be more willing to join.
- Leaflets and/or brochures could include FAQs based on the results of the Co-creation sessions done along WP2 with the aim of resolving the main doubts that people may have.
- All dissemination materials should include contact information (phone number, email address, physical address...).
- Make use of keywords to secure the SENDER programme visibility.

5.1.1.2. Events

Code: REC02

Pilot: All; of especial importance for W.E.I.Z. and ADEE, and less of a priority for VTT according to data.

Time period: April 2022 – October 2022

Duration: One day per event

Target group: General public; see Variations for targeted engagement of: generic late majority, and households with children.

Resources: Mobile or fixed stand, leaflets and/or brochures, one SENDER Box (optional), posters.

Staff: One accredited official with knowledge about demand response and the SENDER programme, two if large attendance is expected; one communication and dissemination official.

Purpose: To make sure that the necessary informative material and content reaches a broad audience, it is relevant to make it accessible through multiple venues. **In-person events** are a key venue for recruitment in European projects of innovation, as they offer a unique opportunity to not only gain awareness of projects, but also to discuss them with experts and representatives, generating higher trust in the population.

Engagement strategy and main actions:

1. Phase 0 (April and May 2022)

Pilots will assess the internal and SENDER-provided budget and resources that are available to them to organise one or multiple informative events. W.E.I.Z and VTT will examine whether between the months of April and October 2022 their own organisations are already holding an event to publicise another energy-related programme, or to raise awareness on a topic broadly related to energy efficiency or sustainability. If so, they will contact the officials in charge of these events and enquire whether it would be possible to destine some time and/or space to inform attendants about SENDER. W.E.I.Z and VTT will also reach out to universities located in their pilot sites for the same purpose, and to explore the possibility of holding a SENDER-specific event for university students and staff. ADEE will do the same with the senior citizen's social club of Alginet, and with local schools.

If SENDER-specific events are feasible, pilots will then book a venue on an available date. This can be both a space owned by the pilot organisation, or an external facility (e.g., the Garden of Generations¹⁴ in the case of W.E.I.Z). The date and time of events should be chosen in accordance with the local working and school schedules in order to maximise attendance. They should not overlap with locally-relevant dates and events.

2. Communication Campaign (One month prior to the date of the event)

Pilots will develop and implement a communication plan to inform the population of this/these event(s). This plan should include a) potential multipliers with whom to liaise for the communication campaign; b) a calendar to contact these multipliers, to share dissemination posts on social media, and to hang posters in public spaces (optional); key messages to attract attendants and the agenda of the event(s).

¹⁴ Tourismus Region Weiz. (2020). Garten Der Generationen. Retrieved from <https://www.tourismus-weiz.at/branchenverzeichnis/garten-der-generationen/>

3. Organising and hosting the event

These events can be organised in very diverse ways. Nevertheless, it is indispensable that all of them include a **free-access stand** in which attendees can learn about domestic energy efficiency, and how the SENDER Box helps in this regard. Information should be available in the form of **leaflets and brochures** attendants can take away. The reach and impact of information sharing would be highly enhanced if in the stands attendees could discuss details of the SENDER project with accredited officials. These stands should either also have the necessary **forms and support material** to enable people to register for participation, or otherwise clear information on the possible ways through which to register should be included in the leaflets and brochures.

Variations: Building on the data analysis conducted for each of the pilot sites, the following variations to informative events can boost the reach of these events by offering a targeted approach aimed at attracting collectives other than pioneers and early innovators.

- **To target the late majority:** Building on the experience of pilots and of the consortium, these events could be organised as ‘informative cafes’. That is, they should be advertised as an opportunity to grab a drink, or some food while learning about an innovative, green, comfort-enhancing programme that will be implemented locally, and from which people have the opportunity to benefit. An engaging structure for such an event would be the following. First, the distribution of an initial drink (e.g., an attractive coffee or a tea). Second, the presentation of the SENDER programme, including a video or infographics on how it works domestically, the technical and environmental benefits it intends to deliver. Third, a timeline of the programme, a short summary of participant responsibilities, and the registration venues available should also be presented clearly. Finally, the most appealing or copious food or drink offerings should be distributed, and the event could continue informally, combining the socialisation and sense of leisure of attendants, and the possibility to ask further questions to SENDER officials.
- **To target households with children: Playground or activities for children:** Innovation Centre Weiz has identified that including a playground or some activities for children is a best practice for information campaigns in which families constitute a relevant target segment. Given that the results of the analysis evince that household with children are a key target for engagement in the three pilots, holding **children-inclusive events** could also be an effective incentive to promote attendance.
- There could be a **sequence of such events**, with variations.

Effective combination of strategies: This strategy can be combined with all strategies of phase 1.

Highlights:

- Use an easy and understandable language, the energy topic is not very attractive to the general population since it is perceived as something hard to understand.
- Leaflets and/or brochures could include FAQs also based on the results of the Co-creation sessions done along WP2 with the aim of resolving the main doubts that people may have.
- All dissemination materials should include contact information (phone number, email address, physical address...)
- Partnering with key multiplier can maximise the project visibility within different events (i.e., counting with the mayor’s support in the case of W.E.I.Z.)

- **For VTT:** Since the Finnish pilots includes three cities, holding an event at each of these should be explored as this could substantially enhance recruitment.

5.1.1.3. Energy efficiency workshops

Code: REC03

Pilot: All

Time period: Once in the Recruitment Phase, preferably in September 2022. ADEE will also use this strategy in the Consumer Response Phase.

Duration: 1-2 hours per workshop / activity

Target Group: General public; see Variations for targeted engagement of: early adopters, medium-high environmentally-aware, and households with children.

Resources: Workshop content, Power Point presentation, projector, computer, low-cost kit for domestic energy efficiency (e.g., efficient bulbs, housing insulation material, timer for electric appliances, thermometer, hydrometers, water-flow reducers), physical venue, SENDER leaflets and brochures, one SENDER Box (optional).

Staff: One accredited official trained in energy advisory for residential customers and acquainted with the SENDER programme; one communication and dissemination official.

Purpose: To convey the positive impact that DR can have economically, environmentally, and in terms of sustainability, and its relationship with SENDER as a solution for citizens.

Engagement strategy and main actions:

1. Phase 0 (April – August 2022)

Pilots will assess the internal capacity of their organisations to hold energy efficiency workshops. First, this will entail an examination of similar events already programmed, that could be simultaneously used to inform attendants on the SENDER programme and on demand response more broadly. W.E.I.Z will enquire whether the energy efficiency workshops organise by the Weiz Energy Agency could be utilised for this purpose. If this internal partnership is possible, a workshop program befitting both the original focus and the demand response focus that SENDER requires will be jointly developed.

Otherwise, pilots will assess whether they could book a venue (e.g. a room) owned by the pilot organisations to hold these events.

2. Communication Campaign (Three weeks prior to the date of the event)

Pilots will develop and implement a communication plan to inform the population of this workshop. This plan should include a) potential multipliers with whom to liaise for the communication campaign; b) a calendar to contact these multipliers, to share dissemination posts on social media, and to hang posters in public spaces (optional); key messages to attract attendants and the agenda of the event(s).

3. *Organising and hosting the workshop*

Workshops and activities can be organized in public facilities which already have their own programme and audience, and which should be **free for all attendees**. The fact that these facilities can also help to disseminate the activities can help to reach a wider audience. These workshops should include:

- Introduction to Energy, Power, Energy demand among other concepts
- Low-cost measures to increase energy efficiency at home (insulation, retrofit of appliances, etc.)
- Daily habits to increase domestic energy efficiency, ways to optimise energy usage, how to reduce the energy bills, etc.
- Introduction to Demand Response as a way to deepen the optimization of energy usage at home, showing how it is compatible with renewable energy installations, vehicle to building, adapting usage according to fluctuations on energy price (if applies), and peer to peer energy trading.
- Presenting SENDER as a solution to enhance the concepts previously discussed. If possible, bringing a SENDER box and showing its operation can generate more interest.

Moreover, information about the project and the recruitment process should be given in hand as **leaflets and brochures** so the attendees can decide at home whether they want to participate or not and they have all the description and contact information available.

Variations:

- **To target the youth:** Workshops can be organized in universities as Living Labs - creating solutions for W.E.I.Z. and VTT.
- **To target families:** Workshops and activities can be organized in schools, approaching daily energy habits, efficiency, and DR as a game to play at home. Making DR a family activity where all members can learn together deepens their engagement. Additionally, to reach more reluctant families, workshops can be advertised and approached as offering opportunities for tight-schedule families to be more energy-efficient without having to alter their schedules and routines.
- **ADEE:** Survey data indicated that people over 65 may be especially interested in assisting to in-person workshops. The pilot can explore to disseminate information on these workshops through the senior citizen's social club of Alginet, and other venues frequented by this age segment. The pilot can also evaluate the adaptation of one or more of the workshops to the interest and accessibility requirements of those over 60-65.

Effective Combination of strategies: This strategy can be combined with strategies REC01, REC02, REC04 and REC05.

Highlights:

- Information provided in the workshops should always highlight the benefits to the end-users. It is important that they perceive that all actions towards energy efficiency will benefit them and not the big energy companies. We aim to generate trust.
- Leaflets and/or brochures could include FAQs also based on the results of the Co-creation sessions done along WP2 with the aim of resolving the main doubts that people may have.

- Use an easy and understandable language, the energy topic is not very attractive to the general population since it is perceived as something hard to understand.
- **For VTT:** Since the Finnish pilots includes three cities, holding one workshop at each of these should be explored as this could substantially enhance recruitment.

5.1.1.4. *Involving social care workers' voice*

Code: REC04

Pilot: N/A; all pilots elected not to make use of this strategy for the SENDER programme.

Time period: Recruitment Phase

Duration: 1 month formation, 1 month communication

Target Group: Vulnerable people, late elderly.

Resources: N/A

Staff: Official with knowledge of demand response and the SENDER programme, one or more social care worker(s)

Purpose: Bring DR closer to those groups by contacting **social care workers**, with whom they have a bond of trust, being them the ones who encourage these potential users to take part in SENDER.

Engagement strategy and main actions: The action consists of two phases:

- Firstly, group meetings with social care workers to present SENDER, focusing on the benefits it can have on people they are working with daily. The meetings should include detailed **information in physical format** (leaflets and brochures) as well as **guidance** regarding the registration process.
- Secondly, those social workers will have bilateral meetings with the target group presenting SENDER and inviting them to participate in the project, taking advantage of the existing bond of trust they have and their knowledge on how to address these users.

Variations: The second phase can be done not only with social workers but also together with support from the SENDER team, specially to explain more technical and administrative aspects of the programme.

Effective Combination of strategies: Social workers can also encourage target groups to attend at workshops, events or other activities related with the project (REC02, REC03, REC05). Additionally, this strategy can be combined with REC01 and registration strategies, REC06 and REC07.

Highlights:

- Use an easy and understandable language, the energy topic is not very attractive to the general population since it is perceived as something hard to understand.

- Including social services care workers can help as a first filter, since they have a deep knowledge on the people they work with and could easily identify who may be interested and who may not, resulting in a more effective recruitment process.

5.1.1.5. Individualised assessment of DR benefits

Code: REC05

Pilot: All

Time period: April 2022 – October 2022; ADEE may also use this strategy in the Consumer Response Phase.

Duration: If offered in-person: 5-10 minutes per enquiry

Target Group: General public; see Variations for EV Owners (VTT)

Resources: N/A

Staff: Official with knowledge of demand response and the SENDER programme, one communication and dissemination official

Purpose: DR and the provision of flexibility are unknown terms to many and gaining knowledge about them by oneself can be overwhelming. To build trust, better inform potential users and solve doubts of interested individuals, pilots could offer potential participants the option to receive an assessment of what gains, changes in behaviour and responsibilities participating in the SENDER programme would mean for them individually.

Engagement strategy and main actions:

1. Phase 0 (April – August 2022)

W.E.I.Z and ADEE will assess the internal capacity of their organisations to offer this service alongside strategies REC02 and REC03. ADEE will also notify and provide the necessary training material to the person in charge of customer services for SENDER, to capacitate him/her to offer this service to users, if they visit ADEE's facilities requesting it. The hour range and dates in which this service can be requested through in-person visits should also be defined and clearly communicated in the following step.

2. Communication Campaign

Pilots will develop and implement a communication plan to inform the population of the possibility to obtain an individualised assessment. This plan should include a) a calendar to share dissemination posts on social media, and to create and hang posters in public spaces (optional); key messages to attract potential participants. Pilots who validate this strategy shall also make sure that information advertising this service is included in the informative materials prepared to raise awareness about SENDER.

3. Service offer

W.E.I.Z and ADEE: Officers trained to provide this service should attend the event or workshop hold in which individualised assessment of benefits will also be made available. It should be made clear to participants whom they need to address to request this service. Officers in charge of this strategy must adapt the assessment to the various contractual formats of participation in the SENDER programme that have been detailed in the deliverable 3.3.

ADEE: As concerns the provision of this service in the pilot's own facilities, the person in charge should be prepared to respond to enquiries on the benefits that interested participants can obtain from SENDER.

VTT: The pilot will prepare a range of housing models and/or a questionnaire that will be uploaded to their website. The housing models and the questions will build on a careful examination, and on the organisation's long-lasting knowledge, of key energy and socioeconomic features of different households in VTT's pilot site. These models and questionnaire will be consulted and filled by interested potential participants and will provide them with key information on how SENDER could benefit them given their housing circumstances, potential for flexibility and level of automation.

Variations: Each pilot may assess which communication channels are the most suitable through which to offer this service.

To target EV Owners, individualised assessment of benefits may also be advertised as offering an evaluation of costs and gains for EV Owners (e.g., scheduling, optimising energy usage). The possibility to integrate Vehicle-to-Building could also be part of the provided assessment.

Another possibility would be establishing a physical information point for certain days at certain times, which participants can go and ask to the reference staff anything related with DR or the project. This approach can be effective when many users could have this information point near to their homes (no more than 10 – 15 minute walk).

Effective Combination of strategies: This strategy can be combined with REC01, REC02, REC03 and REC04.

Highlights:

- Face to face assessment can foster people trust.
- Use an easy and understandable language, the energy topic is not very attractive to the general population since it is perceived as something hard to understand.
- Information provided in the workshops should always highlight the benefits to the end-users. It is important that they perceive that all actions towards energy efficiency will benefit them and not the big energy companies.

5.1.2. Registration

5.1.2.1. Physical registration options

Code: REC06

Pilot: All

Time period: Registration

Duration: N/A, will be confirmed once the registration form is elaborated

Target Group: All

Resources: Registration forms in paper, pens; or one or more tablet(s) or computers; dissemination materials (leaflets, brochures...) with registration information

Staff: If physical registration sites are enabled: Official assisting the process of registration with basic digital skills

Purpose: To respond to concerns related to the COVID-19 pandemic, ease of registration, and to make it possible to potential participants to discuss registration in-detail, increasing people's trust.

Engagement strategy and main actions:

1. Phase 0

To raise awareness about the project and about the different available registration ways, an intense communication action will be required. It is important to provide all necessary information to people, so they can understand SENDER and what will require from them to be part of the programme, so they can feel confident and willing to be part of it. The optimum will be to be able to provide with all the answers to their questions before hand, so the registration process is faster and not perceived as a boring process.

2. Registration process

There will be two registration options in the three project pilots, online (through the SENDER platform) or face-to-face, where users will be able to talk to member of the SENDER programme and make the registration process together and with their support in case it is necessary. Registration ought to include how and what happens if participants opt out. It should also detail how data will be treated and by whom during and after the programme. This process should include information on the definitive rewards, workshops, and activities to which the recruited are entitled to participate and their calendarization will also be studied.

Variations:

- The leaflet will be developed in accordance with the engagement planification and the final use case selection of each pilot. These will also be made available in all the concerned local languages.

- The three pilot agree on having both options available to the public (online and offline registration), nevertheless, VTT will maximise the digital option, since in the case of the Finnish pilot, different cities will be part of the demonstration site, making it a bit more difficult in terms of resources, since one support person for face-to-face registration will not be enough.

Effective Combination of strategies: This strategy can be combined with all phase 1 strategies.

Tips/Highlights:

- Face-to-face registration may provide better registration results, generating trust in the participants and being giving them the opportunity to ask any existing doubts. Additionally, will reduce errors in the collected information in case some technicalities are required.
- Use an easy and understandable language, the energy topic is not very attractive to the general population since it is perceived as something hard to understand.

5.1.2.2. Questionnaire for sustained engagement

Code: REC07

Pilot: All

Time period: Registration

Duration: 5 – 10 minutes

Target Group: All

Resources: Paper questionnaires, pens; or one or more tablet(s) and an online questionnaire

Staff: If physical registration sites are enabled: Official assisting the process of registration with basic digital skills

Purpose: To develop individualised targeted engagement strategies, the collection of various socioeconomic data is necessary to identify population segments manifesting similar needs and preferences for participation in SENDER. While recruitment strategies can be drawn on the insights this deliverable offers based on survey, interviews and user profiling data, targeted strategies for DR and persistence could be improved and further personalised to end-users. This could be done by asking participants to **fill a questionnaire at the moment of/after registration**. This questionnaire will provide pilots and the consortium with information about the key variables that, according to the results of the data analysis this deliverable expounds, are associated with specific demands for long-term engagement in the project. In addition, this questionnaire would be useful to identify people whose environmental awareness or other key factors that would make them more likely to persist throughout the project. Integrating questionnaires with registration is a practice the pilot VTT has previously utilised with success.

Engagement strategy and main actions:

First, W.E.I.Z and ADEE will make an election on whether to integrate this questionnaire with the registration form, or to request participants to fill in both. VTT shall incorporate the questionnaire in the registration forms, if validated.

This questionnaire will include multiple choices, Likert scale and ranking questions, and will be completed by participants in a maximum of 10 minutes. Officials having assisted participants in the process in-person will hand over this questionnaire. If registration has been completed online or over the phone, participants will be notified that they are also requested to fill this questionnaire. It is key that data protection arrangements are established and communicated clearly to participants.

Variations: The base questionnaire will be translated to the local language(s) of each pilot site. Building on the data analysis results, the table below lists the key variables that each pilot should respectively include, as they are the ones displaying a consistent association with specific demands and preferences for sustained engagement.

Table 8: Key variables to consider for the questionnaire for sustained engagement

ADEE	VTT	WEIZ
Education Level	Income	Income
Gender	Gender	Gender
Age	Age	Age
Household Unit	Household Unit	Household Unit
House Ownership	EV Ownership	House Ownership
If feasible: Household composition disaggregated by age	If feasible: Household composition disaggregated by age	If feasible: Household composition disaggregated by age

Effective Combination of strategies: This strategy can be combined with REC06.

Highlights:

- Keep questionnaires short so it is not overwhelming for participants. Including questions that are easy to answer.
- Provide the questionnaire at the same moment other documents (contracts, consent form) are being fulfilled by the participants.
- Count with the option of online and in paper questionnaire, always considering the resources (time) of collecting and analysing the results.

Table 9: Phase 1 – Recruitment strategies key aspects

Code	Name	Pilot	Target	Combined	Highlights
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REC01	Dissemination of informative material in partnership with multipliers	All	General public	All engagement strategies Transversal strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy language • Include FAQs and contact information • Use keywords
REC02	Events	All	General public Variations for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • early adopters • medium-high environmentally aware • households with children 	All strategies from phase 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy language • Include FAQs and contact information • Key multipliers to maximise visibility
REC03	Energy efficiency workshops	All	General public Variations for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • early adopters • medium-high environmentally aware • households with children 	REC01, RECO02, REC04, REC05	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy language • Include FAQs and contact information • Highlight the benefits to the end-users first
REC04	Involving social care worker's voice	All	Vulnerable people Late elderly	All strategies from phase 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy language • Social workers can act as a first recruitment filter
REC05	Individualised assessment of DR benefits	All	General public Variations for EV owners (VTT)	REC01, REC02, REC03, REC04	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy language • Face-to-face when possible • Highlight the benefits to the end-users first
REC06	Physical registration options	All	All	All strategies from phase 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy language • Face-to-face when possible
REC07	Questionnaire for sustained engagement	All	All	REC06	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short questionnaire • Provide the questionnaire together with other documents • Consider online and in paper options

5.2. Phase 2: Consumer Response

Figure 6: Consumer Response strategies

5.2.1. Social pressure

Code: COR01

Pilot: All

Time period: All phases

Duration: N/A

Target Group: All (VTT focusing on a city level impact)

Resources: Informative materials, both digital and printed (printed materials may have an additional cost, it needs to be checked with WP9); social media channels; users' and project results

Staff: The pilot team and a local communication and dissemination official if possible. Support from ECO and EQY for the elaboration of materials.

Purpose: To highlight common actions that are being done in the region/neighbourhood by being part of the SENDER programme which have a positive social impact either by mitigating climate change, reducing energy consumption levels, increasing savings and so on. This kind of actions can be perceived as “the right thing” to do, therefore, may foster others to be willing to do the “right thing” too, relying on social norms and values. This strategy can help strengthening the sense of community and belonging, which people tend to appreciate.

Engagement strategy and main actions: This strategy is similar to the gamification strategy (see COR02, section 5.2.1), nevertheless, while gamification is based in competitiveness and depends on how active users are in embracing the different actions to reach some objectives and therefore rewards, this strategy relies on the social norm and social values that the end-users have, by which end-users may feel some sort of “social pressure” to do the “right thing” especially when their neighbours and people on the area are already being part of these actions.

In case of using this strategy, the project partners will have to decide in which phase it is expected to be used, and how exactly they want to use it. This strategy has mainly an engagement purpose and can be used always that you have already some people onboard to share the message. Some options for the implementation of this strategy are:

- *Stating an Instagram (or other social media) challenge:* based on the communication plan that has been already defined and the message it is intended to be shared, a challenge where participants share some of their results could be interesting to motivate others to do the same. This strategy would work better if the already recruited people are active in social media channels.
- *Share the results on social media channels:* by collecting and sharing the SENDER programme results in general terms, like number of people that have already joined the programme, average savings, on so on it will be possible to show the benefits that can be obtained by being part of the programme that many other people are enjoying.
- *Storytelling:* first, it is necessary to contact participants that want to share their experience in the programme. Then, participants can either record themselves in short videos which then can be shared on the different communication channels, or they can participate in some dissemination event in “user experience sessions”. It will be key to keep track on who opinion leaders are, and to actively reach out and recruit them for storytelling, as they may be trusted and well-considered participants with the capacity to persuade others to go further in the optimisation of their energy consumption (REC03, REC07).

Variations: Guaranteeing the visibility of the project results and impacts can be done in different ways depending on the target you are aiming:

- **At city level,** in the case of VTT, it would be interesting to apply this strategy making use of the city channels. In Finland, cities are trying to become more sustainable day by day, therefore, seen what other cities are doing can motivate new ones to implement similar initiatives.
- These actions could be taken at **national level,** seen how the different pilots are doing and trying to motivate participants in order to be their country to one which is doing better.

Effective Combination of strategies: This strategy can be combined with the COR02 (Gamification), depending on the type of interface that will be used. Moreover, can be combined with REC02 (Events) in case active participants participate in some events by explaining their experience in the programme. It can also be combined with phase 3 strategies as PER01 and PER05. Finally, to combine it with strategies REC03 and especially REC07 can help in identifying opinion leaders.

Highlights:

- Highlight the social norms and values without making feel people “guilty” for not being part, it is better to foster the sense of community and willingness to be part of something bigger.
- Watch out with GDPR regulation when sharing information about the participants progress and impacts.
- Avoid negative messages, foster the positive with encouraging messages that hint on how to do best in an easy way.

5.2.2. Gamification

Code: COR02

Pilot: N/A; all pilots elected not to make use of this strategy for the SENDER programme

Time period: From the demonstration and monitoring phase starts and until the end

Duration: 13 months approximately (March'23 – March'24)

Target Group: General public, especially appealing to early adopters

Resources: Social media channels; rewards (economic and non-economic); SENDER platform that allows having gamification

Staff: The pilot team; legal experts for the feasibility of certain rewards; communication team

Purpose: To design gamification strategies to make the experience of using SENDER more appealing to participants, inviting them to use it more often in an enjoyable manner.

Engagement strategy and main actions: Gamification can be done either by (1) having a common platform/dashboard where goals achieved are seen by all participants and can motivate competition between them; or (2) making participants share their results through their social media channels. Nevertheless, the latter option can be a problem since people may not be willing to publicly share their personal data.

To do gamification it is necessary to first define the goals for participants and rewards that will be granted. For that, validate together with legal experts which rewards can be provided to the participants and how. Then decide which the different goals will be and the reward accordingly. Some gamification options can be:

- **Integrating a digital currency.** People would earn coins/tokens as they develop DR actions that have a positive impact whether it may be energy saved, money saved or environmentally friendly actions. The coins/tokens could then be exchanged for:
 - Peer-to-peer trading with other participants.
 - Reduction in the bill depending on the contractual arrangement, where possible.
 - Other prizes available (home appliances, decoration, lights, toys, discounts on local shops, etc.)
- **Unlocking rewards as well as virtual badges** after achieving certain goals, related with a certain level of savings. There could be multiple options. Some possible rewards are home appliances, digital currency, social benefits (to purchase goods at social economy/green stores; theatre, cafe discounts...).
- **Set saving challenges** for given periods of time so that people that complete them can earn points or coins which can be exchanged for goods or social benefits in the future.
- Establish a **savings ranking** among participants, so participants can see the impact of other users and adopt their actions taken, in order to improve their own case. Being at the top should also imply some reward besides social recognition.

Variations: N/A

Effective Combination of strategies: This strategy can be combined with COR01 and COR06.

Highlights:

- Strong and appealing multipliers can help in the identification and implementation of rewards.
- Have an attractive and intuitive interface.
- Legal requirements for giving reward may differ from country to country.

5.2.3. Being part of the installation process

Code: COR03

Pilot: All

Time period: Installation process

Duration: Day (s) of installation

Target Group: General public mainly early adopters, households with children, and youth under 35.

Resources: Explanatory video; Installation manual; other informative materials containing tips, contact information, FAQs, between others

Staff: The pilot team and a local communication and dissemination official if possible; Support of ECO and EQY

Purpose: To include the household in the installation process, not only by deciding its location inside the house but also by explaining them how the device will work and what will it do, giving the user a couple of tips on how to solve minor problems that may arise.

Engagement strategy and main actions:

1. Preparation of communication materials

All communication materials need to be prepared following the communication plan. To make participants part of the installation process, a **short video** can be prepared explaining what is being installed, what does this exactly do, what kind of interactions the participants can/need to have with the installed appliances, how long the installation process will last, and other relevant information for participants to have. Additionally, an **installation manual for users** could be developed, including the same information that the video includes but in a more detailed manner. This manual should also include how user can do to solve minor issues with the installed appliances, so they can try by themselves first. Finally, other material can be produced with really schematic information, like quick tips or FAQs, some possible formats for these materials are flyers, brochures and magnets. It is worth noting that some of the mentioned materials can be both digital and non-digital.

2. Introducing the installation process to participants

As already mentioned in previous strategies, it is important for participants to have as much information as possible when signing in for being part of the SENDER programme. Therefore, once all materials are produced, project pilots need to decide how to share them with the participants, some options are:

- Provide all this information right after the registration phase, by sending an email with the corresponding attachments, or granting access to some user area in the platform.
- Provide all this information right after scheduling the installation visit, by sending an email with the corresponding attachments, or granting access to some user area in the platform.
- Sharing the video during events and other informative sessions, giving participants the possibility to ask questions in case of doubts.
- Making the installer have a QR could share with the participants the moment he/she arrives to the households, so user can watch the video and download the manual at the moment. This alternative may imply the installer to answers more questions than expected, which may take a longer time in the installation process.

3. *Other ways of including participants in the installation process*

According to empirical research, participants of DR are more likely to participate if the smart meter is located **somewhere visible**, and therefore not easily forgotten. Location should be agreed on with participants each time, taking this into account the technical requirements that the device requires.

Variations: N/A

Effective Combination of strategies: N/A

Highlights:

- Consider any support materials to be delivered to the participants in the moment of installation when designing the communication plan: these materials ought to be fully devised prior to the implementation of this strategy.
- Consider the target audience for deciding which type of materials or training/explanation process will work better.
- All materials need to be produced with a none-technical language.
- Participants need to understand what exactly the devices do and what kind of interactions can they have with them, giving them a certain **level of autonomy** to solve minor issues

5.2.4. The Sender Box

Code: COR04

Pilot: N/A; as concerns the SENDER programme, this strategy cannot be implemented by pilots. Instead, this strategy will inform the selection of resources to be installed as part of WP7. This strategy is nonetheless of marked relevance for future demand response programmes.

Time period: Design and selection period of the SENDER Box and its supporting resources

Duration: N/A

Target Group: General public

Resources: To be determined in WP7

Staff: Qualified officers in charge of the selection of supporting resources in WP7

Purpose: People are not willing to give up the **cosiness and comfort** of the domestic space. The programming of the demands and adjustments proposed by the SENDER Box should limit interference with the usual practices and habits of the house, and it should benefit its physical appearance. Also, the design of the SENDER Box can boost engagement if it increases people's knowledge about the energy sector to make better decisions in the future, as to what type of appliances are more efficient, which ones consume more or less, and what consumptions can be more easily reduced.

Engagement strategy and main actions: Modern, suggestive colours, graphics of smart meters are highly praised by users (Hargreaves, 2010). When designing the physical appearances of the SENDER Box and the infographics it will display, these features should be included in a feasible manner. Designing the SENDER Box with the aim of having an attractive, **eye-catching appearance** may help to sustain engagement and to develop a sense of attachment to the SENDER Box. In fact, among survey respondents from VTT pilot, aesthetical appearance was ranked as a relevant priority regarding the election of new technologies. And in the case of W.E.I.Z., this property was rated as significantly important, on average, by those aged below 35. Furthermore, it is of also of especial importance for information communicated by the SENDER Box to be meaningful and understandable to the user. This relates to the measures selected to convey information about energy consumed or saved. According to research, expressing it in monetary terms is the most widely understandable measure to display in smart meters (ibid). SENDER Box designers could also study the possibility of offering multiple choices regarding the type and measurement of data to be displayed.

Variations: Designers will assess possible options to take into consideration and implement these guidelines. The smart meter could also show information on the energy consumption of the house disaggregated by appliance, analysis of consumption patterns, or suggestions to optimise energy use.

Effective Combination of strategies: This strategy can be combined with COR03.

Highlights:

- Include infographics that help with the aesthetical aspects.
- Provide support materials that are easy to understand.

5.2.5. Phone follow-up

Code: COR05

Pilot: All

Time period: First six-months

Duration: Once per month, call length: 5 – 10 minutes

Target Group: Elderly and vulnerable households

Resources: One telephone or a WhatsApp dissemination list (optional), a list of phone contact details of the target participants

Staff: An accredited official with knowledge about demand response and the SENDER programme

Purpose: To keep track of people's perception, to ask for feedback, and to give assistance, if necessary, about SENDER. This strategy will be specifically designed to assist vulnerable households and the elderly, since they may face additional difficulties in accessing digital content, may have specific necessities in terms of energy consumption, and are likely to inhabit apartments or houses in need of rehabilitation (Maller & Strengers, 2011).

Engagement strategy and main actions:

1. Identification of participants who could benefit from this assistance

After recruitment, the pilots will rely on the questionnaires filled at registration, and on the information learnt during installation to elaborate a list of participants who may benefit from phone follow-up.

2. Trial of the preliminary list of candidates for phone follow-up (30 days after installation)

After 30 days since installation, a first round of phone follow-ups will be conducted with all the shortlisted participants. In the follow-up, the officer will ask participants about (a) whether they have performed any change in their domestic energy consumption, (b) if any inconvenience or problem with SENDER has arisen and (c) if they would like to be offered some tips to go further in enhancing their energy efficiency and in participating in demand response. If participants report some relevant difficulty that they cannot solve by themselves, the officer in charge of the phone follow-up will make sure that participants receive the necessary support.

Subsequently, the officer will ask participants if they consider that the support just received was helpful, and if they wish to continue to be contacted monthly. In this manner, participants who do not want or need this service will be able to opt out voluntarily, and a definitive list will be elaborated.

3. Monthly follow-up

For half a year, every month the officer in charge will make phone calls to participants. The calls should provide relevant and useful information to users, such as the money saved thanks to SENDER, the energy saved, etc. using colloquial language easy to understand, as well as new DR recommendations. On the other hand, phone calls can also be useful to gather feedback from participants about the SENDER box, its usage, the perception of the project, etc.

Variations:

VTT: Instead of phone calls, the pilot will consider utilising a WhatsApp dissemination list to have more direct communication with the participants and also for disseminating general information that may affect them all. This strategy was used in a local project, led by Ecoserveis, with vulnerable families and worked very well.

ADEE: In addition to the phone follow-up, ADEE may also establish a monthly videocall, to which all SENDER participants shall be invited. To join these calls will always be voluntary. In these videocalls, participants will have the possibility to discuss their experience of SENDER, to solve doubts and problems.

Effective Combination of strategies: This strategy can be combined with REC07, COR04, COR06, PER01, PER03, PER04, PER05.

Highlights:

- In case of thinking of creating a WhatsApp group for communication purposed you will need to have to include that in the Consent Form to be sign by the participants.
- Depending on the number of users you may require additional resources.

5.2.6. Social benefits

Code: COR06

Pilot: All

Time period: At the end of the project, or to be unblocked after a target of energy efficiency has been reached by participants

Duration: N/A

Target Group:

Table 10: Target groups for the different pilots

ADEE	VTT	WEIZ
General Public	Households with children	General Public
Households with children	Youth under 35	Households with children
		Youth under 35

Resources: SENDER budget (allocated to the social benefit elected by the pilot)

Staff: N/A

Purpose: The periodical or eventual provision of social benefits to those who participate, or who surpass a minimum threshold of energy savings, could be a useful means to keep people actively involved in DR, and to maintain or enhance a positive perception of the project. The goal of these social benefits would be to ensure that people remain participative and well-informed about DR, until the adoption of the SENDER Box and the change in domestic energy consumption habits is normalised. In contrast with gamification, which rewards best performers, social benefits are **unlocked** as a result of merely long-term engagement, or by setting targets that are easily achievable to all. In this manner, engagement of households with more difficulty in adapting their energy consumption schedules can also be fostered.

Engagement strategy and main actions: Social benefits is a broad term to refer to various gifts, discounts, and free pass to activities participants will find available to themselves after a given time of engagement in the programme, or after attaining a specified reduction in energy consumption. The Future Consumer Research Group of VTT has previously utilised this strategy with success and recommended it as a best practice in one of the expert interviews hold. As concerns the pilot, social benefits such as quality food baskets, cinema tickets or passes for other cultural events were utilised.

In order to be coherent with SENDER's goal of promoting sustainable lifestyles, social benefits such as free locally produced organic food baskets, discounts for socially-minded local goods, services and events, workshops, courses or energy-efficient appliances could be considered.

1. Definition of social benefit, its quantity, and access scheme (April 2022 – June 2022)

The SENDER programme allocates a budget of 10,000€ per pilot to be used in engagement strategies. Each pilot will first choose what social benefit they intend to make available for participants. This choice addresses the (a) type or content of the social benefit, (b) the quantity of such social benefit(s) to be distributed, (c) the scheme through which participants will be able to opt for these benefits, and (d) a calendar for their allocation. While this decision will be taken by pilots in the coming months, these are the preliminary guidelines for social benefits that each pilot is presently considering:

- **ADEE:** The pilot intends to provide a social benefit to all participants, dividing the SENDER budget equally among them. They may use as a social benefit an energy efficiency kit. This kit would allow participants to gain further knowledge on the topic, and to better engage in demand response. The energy efficiency kits would be made available to participant after participants have remained engaged in the programme for a substantial amount of time, and after attaining some energy efficiency target(s).
- **VTT:** The pilot will elect the social benefit to be distributed, if any, in accordance with the organisation's updated internal regulation on incentives for engagement. VTT also favours the equal division of budget among all participants.
- **W.E.I.Z:** The Austrian pilot has a recruitment target of 200 participants. As such, the pilot will meticulously assess the convenience of equally dividing the budget among participants, or to do one lottery or a limited range of lotteries, raffling high-quality products.

2. Communication Actions

After the social benefit has been chosen, the type, quantity and access scheme of social benefits should be included in the various materials and communications plans developed as part of the informative campaign (REC01). In this manner, social benefits and their advertisement can be useful in fostering engagement throughout recruitment, consumer response and persistence.

Variations:

- **Incentive for recruitment:** While social benefits can be highly instrumental in incentivising initial behavioural change, they can also be an additional motivation for potential participants to register. Consequently, in the various strategies deployed as part of the information campaign, the offer of the selected social benefits could be communicated (e.g., in leaflets, events...).
- **Appealing to the desire of not falling behind:** Social benefits could be offered in a manner that incentivises specific, easily attainable to all, behavioural changes, by means of providing benefits to those who firstly do so. For instance, by offering a given number (e.g., 50) discounts in efficient white appliances to the first participants who reach a given target of reduced consumption, or of flexibility provision. Another alternative, where possible, could be to provide a limited number of special offers for people to join local energy cooperatives.

- **Single lottery format:** Instead of offering a larger number of social benefits, a single, more valuable, lottery could be raffled among those who attain a given target of flexibility provision or reduction in energy consumption. In this case, it is important to make sure that the prize is attractive to the wider population, and that its quality is credible enough to boost engagement. For instance, by raffling the installation of PV panels, or shares of PV stations.

Variations will also concern the social benefit chosen, if any, and whether there will be single or multiple ones distributed over time for each participant complying with the requirements. To make it more appealing, participants that qualify for social benefits could be able to choose from a limited range of reward options.

Effective Combination of strategies: To also function as a recruitment incentive, this strategy could be deployed jointly with REC01, REC02, REC03, REC04, REC05.

Highlights:

- Always be transparent and equative with the participants, you do not want to lose their trust may making differences between them. Some pilots like VTT have suggested that in case of having social benefits they should be given to everyone, otherwise it will be unfair to the participants.
- To retain participants active involvement throughout the project it is recommended to include the lottery in the contract and after a certain time of active commitment, otherwise it gives a wrong message and foster the participation of people who are not really interested in the project but in the social benefits themselves.
- Legal requirements for giving reward may differ from country to country.

Table 11: Phase 2 - Consumer Response strategies key aspects

Code	Name	Pilot	Target	Combined	Tips
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COR01	Social pressure	All	All	REC02 COR02 PER01 PER05	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highlight the social norms and values not fostering guilt • Watch out with GDPR regulation • Avoid negative messages
COR02	Gamification	N/A	General public Especially appealing to early adopters	PER01 PER02	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong and appealing multipliers • Attractive and intuitive interface • Check legal requirements
COR03	Being part of the installation process	All	General public Especially appealing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • early adopters • households with children • youth under 35 	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support materials to be delivered according to the target • Easy language
COR04	The SENDER Box	No pilots, but SENDER programme in general	General public	COR03	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include infographics that help with the aesthetical aspects • Support materials that are easy to understand
COR05	Phone follow up	All	Elderly and vulnerable people	REC07 COR04 COR06 PER01 PER03 PER04 PER05	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Watch out with GDPR regulations • May require additional resources
COR06	Social benefits for participation	All	ADEE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General Public • Households with children W.E.I.Z. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Households with children • Youth under 35 VTT <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Households with children • Youth under 35 	REC01 REC02 REC03 REC04 REC05	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transparent and equative • Include the lottery in the contract and after a certain time of active commitment to give the right incentive • Check legal requirements

5.3. Phase 3: Persistence

Figure 7: Persistence strategies

5.3.1. Online forum

Code: PER01

Pilot: All

Time period: Available since registration

Duration: N/A

Target Group: All

Resources: Online platform (SENDER dashboard, Facebook, Telegram Group)

Staff: One accredited official with knowledge about demand response and the SENDER programme; support from ECO and EQY; support from IT experts, if necessary

Purpose: To boost the sense that the SENDER Box and the adaptation of domestic energy behaviour is not something a given household is doing in isolation, but alongside other similar households. Having an online platform where participants can share their experience and doubts can foster trust, a sense of belonging and of acting for a common cause and consolidate their determination to participate.

Engagement strategy and main actions:

1. *Definition of platform to be used, the access scheme and allocated resources.*

The best scenario would be to have an integrated platform/dashboard in the SENDER website, which participants could access by creating an account and password. In case this option is not available, each pilot will need to decide which platform to use, at this point, Telegram seems to be a good option, since it is easy to use, well-known, people do not need to provide personal data and allows sharing different kind of information. Other options are (1) Facebook private groups, where participants will be invited, this alternative was used previously by ADEE and in their experience it was not very active;

and (2) WhatsApp groups, which could also be an option within small communities that are willing to share their experience between them. If the selected platform allows it, it would be important to consider the integration of each participant's username in the programme with a SENDER account to the platform.

Once the platform is clear, it is essential for the pilots to assign at least one specialized officer to be part of the forum so he/she can answer the existing questions on a regular basis. Additionally, a set of rules should be defined for participants to follow, securing respect between participants and everyone's security.

2. Communication actions

The existence of the online forum should be highly disseminated, so participants are aware of its existence and how to use it, allowing the SENDER programme to take a full advantage of the benefits of having the platform, like (1) foster faster resolution of doubts, since participants will be able to look on the platform if someone has had the same doubt before and has already been answered; and (2) motivate early adopters and beta testers (PER02), people with a higher technical knowledge, to act as monitors to their neighbours, motivated by social recognition. Therefore, communication and dissemination actions on the existence of the forum should be included since recruitment.

3. *Online forum management*

As already stated, at least one specialized officer should be included in the group to manage all inquiries and making sure that the established rules are being followed accordingly.

Variations: The online forum can serve as a place to communicate key information about the programme, to pass evaluation surveys, and to collect participants' feedback. Additionally, it can be used as the first step for the creation a more active group, where people motivate each other. This mutual motivation

Effective Combination of strategies: could be combined with the PER02, PER03.

Highlights:

- Participants should have access to the platform from the very beginning.
- Information should be available in the participants' language.
- The forum should be supervised and keep active by some member of the SENDER project.
- Consider the best option according to the target audience (Facebook, Telegram...)

5.3.2. *Becoming beta testers*

Code: PER02

Pilot: All

Time period: From installation until the end of the programme

Duration: N/A

Target Group: Early Adopters

Resources: Communication platform utilised in strategy PER01 (e.g., Telegram, Facebook, other).

Staff: Official with knowledge of demand response and the SENDER programme

Purpose: To give the opportunity to early adopters and highly motivated participants to provide feedback on the implementation of the pilots' use cases, to know whether they consider things should be done differently and/or what additional aspects should be included. This action can be included as part as the co-creation process already done within SENDER but taking it to a further stage. The ultimate goal is to collect information on potential improvements of the SENDER Box, and to make a range of users feel more engaged as they will have a saying, and they will perceive an enhanced sense of responsibility and cooperation.

Engagement strategy and main actions:

1. Communication Actions

The possibility to become beta starters should be communicated to interested users in the informative campaign (REC01), especially in social media posts during the Recruitment Phase.

After installation concrete information reminding users that they can operate as beta testers and how to do so ought to be provided to all participants via email. Further, on the online forum that pilots are considering establishing in PER01, SENDER officers will enable channels through which beta testers can provide their feedback. They will also post in the online forum a reminder notifying participants that it is possible for them to compose feedback.

2. Collecting beta tester feedback

Beta testers should receive monthly enquiries regarding their experience and responding to this ought to remain always optional.

To make it more attractive for beta testers to repeatedly collaborate, monthly enquiries could be tied to information regarding real problems affecting the management of the grid, or broader issues in the renewable energy transition, which DR contributes to solve. In this manner, beta testers could be asked on matters such as the level of flexibility the average user can offer and how, what they think they lack to engage in peer-to-peer trading, to synchronise with the generation of RES, and so forth. The most active beta testers could receive **rewards** in the form of digital currency (see strategy COR02), and their status as beta testers could be incorporated into their user profile in the online forum (see strategy PER01).

Additionally, if beta tester feedback should be incorporated in any adaptation of the programme or the SENDER Box, this must be communicated to all beta testers. This will serve as additional recognition and as proof that their opinions are taken into due consideration. If beta testers highlight relevant shortcomings, SENDER officer's ought to respond in due time, and where possible seek to amend the identified downfalls.

Variations: N/A

Effective Combination of strategies: This strategy could be effectively combined with PER01, integrating beta testing and the participant online forum in a single platform. For rewards, it could be combined with strategy COR02.

Highlights:

- Include the fact of being a beta tester in the contract with all relevant information to it.
- Pay attention to all suggestions to avoid beta testers to opt-out.
- Make sure that the platform used for this strategy is the same as in strategy PER01, in order not to duplicate information, and to enhance a positive user experience.

5.3.3. Guidance to adopt further energy efficiency measures

Code: PER03

Pilot: All, of especial importance for W.E.I.Z. and ADEE; of interest for targeted engagement for VTT

Time period: From the deployment and installation phase onwards

Duration: N/A

Target Group:

Table 12: Target groups per pilot to PER03 strategy

ADEE	VTT	WEIZ
General Public (83% of demand among survey respondents)	Households with children	General Public (89% of demand among survey respondents)
Households with children		Households with children
Youth under 35		

Resources: Depending on the guidance structure, workshop content, Power Point presentation, projector, computer, low-cost kit for domestic energy efficiency (e.g., efficient bulbs, housing insulation material, timer for electric appliances, thermometer, hygrometers, water-flow reducers), physical venue, SENDER leaflets and brochures, updated information on existing funds, grants, and other related programs.

Staff: One accredited official acquainted with the SENDER programme; one communication and dissemination official, if necessary

Purpose: For those people with a notable level of **environmental awareness** that seek a further knowledge about energy and sustainability, it is worth to provide them with tools and/or connections with other stakeholders so they can extend further their impact besides the project and entrench pro-environmental attitudes and behaviours.

Engagement strategy and main actions: There are many different actions that could be done to accomplish this purpose, these actions will vary depending on the type of guidance that is intended to provide.

1. *Preparation of workshops as guidance toward EE measures*

In case the guidance measures are **workshops** and other related educational sessions, materials such as presentations and printed materials will need to be elaborated. Then, the session should be organised, looking for a venue (physical) or setting an online session. To continue, the “event” should be disseminated to reach the expected number of participants. Additionally, contacting an expert in the field who can participate in a webinar or face to face meeting showing best practices and measures, and share information about previously searched local stakeholders who can help (if necessary) the local participants to replicate such best practices.

The organisation of workshops is more detailed as part of Phase 1: Recruitment strategies, more concretely REC03 (Section 5.1.1.3 of this document).

2. Informative action as guidance toward EE measures

In this case, a pilot official should be updated on existing funds, grants and other related initiatives and send general and simple informative mails including this information to the participants, therefore, a mailing list should be created as a first step. The frequency of these mails should not be high, so not to overwhelm people with constant messages. Nevertheless, the messages aim at raising awareness on energy efficiency topics to foster actions such as the installation of PV systems and other energy efficiency measures, measure on which people tend to be interested but many times do not know where or how to start. This strategy aims at giving users that first push, from a trustworthy network.

Variations: Alternative guidance measures that can be provided are guided visits to certain buildings with integrated solutions that go beyond SENDER could be organized. Also, to certain industries or enterprises that can provide tailored solutions to be integrated in a household. In addition, a leaflet including building solutions and local providers that could be delivered to participants after a certain period has passed since the beginning of the project. And to even go beyond, other fields related with environmental impact can be considered, e.g., food, waste, consumption of goods, materials, tourism, etc.

Opinion leaders: Another variation could explore the engagement of participants previously identified as opinion leaders. In this case, it would be necessary for these opinion leaders to have performed very well in terms of the energy efficiency and demand response objectives of the programme, or to have engaged in actions that were beyond the scope of the programme. To engage fellow participants in this task may facilitate the provision of practical, replicable advice to participants interested in going further on the matter of energy sustainability.

Effective Combination of strategies: some of those actions could be combined with PER04 together to create a deeper experience.

Highlights:

- Pay attention to people eager to learn more and go further, this people could be essential for the replication of the model.
- Be updated on the energy efficiency topic to be considered a referent.

5.3.4. Cycle of exhibitions

Code: PER04

Pilot: All

Time period: N/A, Specific to each pilot

Duration: N/A, Specific to each pilot

Target Group: All

Resources: Projector, posters, venue, exhibition panels, microphones, food and drink offerings (optional), additional resources depending on the format of the exhibition

Staff: Two officers with knowledge about demand response and the SENDER programme, one communication officer, additional personnel depending on the format of the exhibition

Purpose: To convey the need for DR and user proactive actions as a response to an unsustainable energy model. Exhibition is used in this deliverable as a broad term encompassing activities that involve in-person attendance, and that range from the elaboration of informative panels, the projection of a documentary, workshops to roundtables to discuss user experiences with food or drink offerings.

Engagement strategy and main actions:

1. Phase 0: Capacity assessment and exhibition planning

Pilots will conduct an assessment of partnerships that SENDER could establish with other exhibitions developed by the pilot organisations, if any, as well as with relevant multipliers in the pilot sites. These other exhibitions or events should also be broadly related with the themes of citizens as actors for sustainability, energy efficiency, the relevance of flexibility for the energy transition and demand response. If these partnerships are possible, an exhibition befitting both the original focus and the demand response focus that SENDER requires will be jointly developed. Otherwise, pilots will assess whether they could book a venue (e.g. a room) owned by the pilot organisations to hold these events.

2. Communication Campaign

Pilots will develop and implement a communication plan to inform the population of these exhibitions. This plan should include a) an email template to share with SENDER participants informing them that they can attend this event, as well as volunteer to share their experience and co-present SENDER, b) potential multipliers with whom to liaise for the communication campaign; c) a calendar to share dissemination posts on social media, and to hang posters in public spaces (optional).

3. Organising and hosting the exhibition

Pilots will concretise the type of exhibition(s) to be hold, and whether these will be open to people who are not SENDER participants themselves. An example of an exhibition format that could be used to illuminate technology's capacity to deliver positive environmental impact, and specifically about the ways in which demand response enables citizens to do so by themselves, could be the following: the

project of Domestic Data Streamers combines the power of storytelling with data to create participatory projects that build community and educate, to craft campaigns that communicate, products that truly connect and exhibitions that make people feel and think with more empathy.

While this will be validated in the coming months, the Finnish pilot VTT may offer the possibility to volunteering participants to share their experience and user insights on the SENDER programme. The exhibition could thus be organised and advertised as an exhibition featuring citizen, bottom-up knowledge of demand response. For participants, the exhibition would therefore constitute an opportunity to further expound their knowledge and difficulties regarding SENDER, to get further feedback and assistance to improve in domestic energy efficiency, and to socialise and grab food and drinks with fellow participants.

Variations: Projecting the attainments so far made through SENDER: Part of an exhibition could be an infographic displaying the results of the project itself, being updated in real time.

Effective Combination of strategies: This strategy can be combined with COR02 (Gamification), PER03, and PER05 to display results obtained in an exhibition.

Highlights:

- Multiple exhibitions that people can visit as a cultural/educative event, featuring information on the usefulness of flexibility services to the energy transition, and illuminating updates on the collective achievements of the SENDER programme.
- Could be led by the pilot partners or co-developed with locally established multipliers.

5.3.5. Capacity to track impact

Code: PER05

Pilot: N/A; it is not in the capacity of pilots to implement this strategy. Should it be made available through the design of the support material of SENDER (e.g., app, website, smart meter), all pilots have manifested that they would utilise it as a persistence strategy.

Time period: Since installation until the end of the programme

Duration: N/A

Target Group: Early adopters; General Public

Resources: Direct communication channels with participants (e.g., email newsletter, a WhatsApp dissemination list), infographics and information summaries

Staff: One communication and dissemination official; an official that analyses data and produces the infographics to be sent (optional)

Purpose: Individuals are willing to change behaviour for collective social and environmental goals if they believe that their actions are impactful (Huijts et al., 2012). A way to consolidate engagement is thus to provide insights in what is achieved in terms of climate change mitigation, better grid management and so forth, through their actions, the actions of those engaged in the same use cases

as them, or their broader community. Similarly, informing the user on how his/her domestic energy consumption has evolved over time because of their involvement in the SENDER programme can further enhance their perception of being empowered to act for individual and collective goals they may deem valuable.

Engagement strategy and main actions: Informative material (e.g., in the form of an email newsletter, a WhatsApp dissemination list, or infographics displayed by the SENDER Box if feasible) should be sent monthly, or every 90 days to participants regarding (1) the evolution of their own consumption and (2) what their change in consumption and/or participation in DR contributes to social and environmental ends. Regarding the first, the general trend could be displayed with graphics to ease understanding, and potentially using money as one, or the single, measure utilised.¹⁵ As concerns impact on collective goals, the effect of one’s own actions alongside those of households with a similar performance in terms of either energy efficiency or DR could be presented in suggestive infographics.

Variations:

- **Justifying DR activation offers:** Each time that a DR activation offer is sent to a participant, this could be accompanied with a concise, understandable explanation of what benefit to the environment, the grid, the energy transition or society, their acceptance of DR contributes to (e.g., doing “this action” implies saving the same of energy consumed by 10 washing cycles)
- **Questionnaires to track change:** Pilots could offer households the option to fill in a questionnaire prior to installation concerning consumption habits, energy use disaggregated by the main appliances or uses of the house and bill expenditure. The same questionnaire could be filled again by interested participants at the end of the programme, in order to assess the change in habits and consumption patterns.

Effective Combination of strategies: This strategy would work effectively in combination with PER01, PER03, COR04, COR06.

Highlights:

- People need to see the benefits of their actions, otherwise, they may see no use in participating.
- Available support for fulfilling the questionnaire with technical information, people may not know where to find it.
- Seeing their improvement in a constant basis will also help seeing how close they are for achieving certain goals/rewards.

Table 13: Phase 3 – Persistence strategies key aspects

Code	Name	Pilot	Target	Combined	Highlights
PER01	Online forum	All	All	PER02 PER03	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access from the beginning • Participants' language • SENDER members supervision

¹⁵ For further reference on the use of money as a metrics for smart meters see section 2.2.6.

PER02	Becoming a beta tester	All	Early adopters	COR02 PER01	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include the fact of being a beta tester in the contract • Pay attention to their suggestions
PER03	Guidance to adopt further energy efficiency measures	All Especial importance for W.E.I.Z. and ADEE Of interest for VTT	ADEE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General Public (83% of demand among survey respondents) • Households with children • Youth under 35 W.E.I.Z. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Households with children VTT <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public (89% of demand among survey respondents) • Households with children 	PER04	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pay attention to people eager to learn more and go further, this people could be essential for the replication of the model. • Be updated, be a referent.
PER04	Cycle of exhibitions	All	All	COR02 PER03 PER05	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural visits/educative events • Local multipliers
PER05	Capacity to track impact	N/A – depend on the programme capacities	Early adopters General Public	PER01 PER02 COR04 COR06	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Show participants their benefits and achievements • Available support for filling the questionnaires

6. Engagement guidelines per pilot country

This section includes a wrap-up of all previously mentioned strategies, for the different engagement phases for each of the pilot countries. To facilitate the use of this information and avoid missing key aspects when deciding which strategies to implement in each specific moment, the information has been collected in a specific **infographic** per project pilot.

6.1. Spain (ADEE) key aspects and strategies to follow

The figure below summarizes the strategies that will be followed by the Spanish pilot (ADEE).

6.2. Finland (VTT) key aspects and strategies to follow

The figure below summarizes the strategies that will be followed by the Finnish pilot (VTT).

6.3. Austria (W.E.I.Z.) key aspects and strategies to follow

The figure below summarizes the strategies that will be followed by the Austrian pilot (W.E.I.Z)

RECRUITMENT PHASE

The 1st step is to define a strong Communication Plan and to identify key multipliers

Start with the INFORMATION CAMPAIGN:

REC01
REC02
REC03

REC04
REC05

Continue with the REGISTRATION PROCESS:

REC06
REC07

Note: Use an easy and non-technical language, include keywords and contact information, always highlight the benefits to the end users and remember that having a face-to-face registration possibility is highly valuable for end-users.

CONSUMER RESPONSE PHASE

COR01
COR03

COR05
COR06

VARIATIONS:

COR05: Make use of videocalls as part of the phone follow-up to be more resource and time efficient.

COR06: Decide between having an equal division or organising a lottery or limited range o lotteries with high quality products.

Note: Use an easy and non-technical language, avoid negative messages, provide support materials, always check the legal requirements, be transparent.

PERSISTENCE PHASE

PER01
PER02

PER03
PER04

VARIATIONS:

PER03: provide guidance to adopt further energy efficiency measures to the different target groups involved.

Note: Use an easy and non-technical language, pay attention to participants' suggestions and to people eager to go further, support must be always available, include local multipliers, be a referent.

7. Next steps

This section details the next steps that are conceived to continue working in the engagement process together with the project pilots, to result both in a successful implementation of the SENDER project and in the validation of the proposed strategies for further replication.

7.1. Engagement process timeline

As previously stated, the first step is to start with what we called “Phase 0”, which starts with the elaboration of a Communication Plan (see Section 4.2). Additionally, to the support and accompaniment that ECO will provide the project pilots with the elaboration of the communication plan that guarantees a successful engagement process, a first timeline has been drafted, as a tool that will allow having a general overview of the different tasks that are expected in the upcoming months. This timeline is done with an engagement perspective and is to be adapted according to the local characteristics when defining the communication plan. It is worth noting that the timeline only includes the strategies that were more attractive and feasible for the project pilots, excluding REC04, COR02, and PER05.

SENDER - Engagement process timeline		Year 2 - 2022						Year 3 - 2023						Year 4 - 2024																			
		Mar.	April	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	April	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	April	May	June	July	Aug.	Sept.	
Code	Strategy	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	
T7.3	Procurement and deployment																																
T7.4	Demonstration and monitoring																																
T7.5	Analysis of the results																																
Phase 0	Pre-engagement actions																																
P0.1	Design of the communication plan																																
P0.2	Contacting potential multipliers																																
P0.3	Elaboration of dissemination materials																																
Phase 1	Recruitment																																
REC01	Dissemination of informative material in partnership with multipliers																																
REC02	Events																																
REC03	Energy efficiency workshops																																
REC05	Individualised assessment of DR benefits																																
REC06	Physical registration options																																
REC07	Questionnaire for sustained engagement																																
Phase 2	Consumer Response																																
COR01	Social pressure																																
COR03	Being part of the installation process																																
COR04	The SENDER Box																																
COR05	Face-to-face or phone follow up																																
COR06	Social benefits for participation																																
Phase 3	Persistence																																
PER01	Online forum																																
PER02	Becoming a beta tester																																
PER03	Guidance to adopt further energy efficiency measures																																
PER04	Cycle of exhibitions																																

Figure 8: Engagement process 1st timeline proposal

7.2. Definition of indicators of engagement

As part of WP7 activities to fulfil the objective of the physical implementation of the solutions in the 3 demonstrations sites and then analyse the impacts and results, a set of indicators of engagement will be defined for the pilot regions. These indicators will help in the one hand, assessing the engagement status at the different implementations phases to correct them if necessary, and on the other hand, evaluating the overall satisfaction level. Having a constant evaluation process based on the continuous improvement methodology will allow improving the engagement strategies and process by:

- Better defining the right order to use the strategies.

- Determining a perfect timing both in terms of when to apply the strategies and the duration that provides better results.
- Understanding what strategies work better with the different target groups and contexts.
- Searching for effective combinations of strategies.
- Identifying the perfect match between different type of incentives that can be uses.
- Make better resources estimations, both in terms of materials and required staff effort.

Besides, the indicators of engagement will allow having an overall understanding of the implementation process from a social and user-centred perspective, which will be essential for the definition of recommendations for the replication of the SENDER programme in different contexts.

8. Annexes

Annex 1: Interview Guidelines

This is the script that was used for the conduction of interviews to pilots' representatives, marketing and consumer group experts from the pilot regions, and members from other BRIDGE initiatives on DR.

INTERVIEW GUIDELINES TO PROJECT PILOTS

INTRODUCTION

1. Short introduction of WP3, and more concretely D3.2 objectives

SECTION 1: DATA ON THE POPULATION OF INTEREST

1. Specify population of interest
2. Existing survey/data bases
3. Contact details to circulate a survey (check the waters first)
4. Intermediary to circulate a survey
5. Expert in anthropology/sociology
6. Expert in marketing campaigns

SECTION 2: CHANNELS AND STRATEGIES FOR USER ENGAGEMENT

7. Previous successful user engagement strategies in the pilot
8. Incentives that could work
9. Available communication channels

SECTION 3: PARTNER KNOWLEDGE OF TARGET GROUPS

10. Popular perception of demand response
11. A priori population segmentation
12. How to compensate hand over control
13. Level of automation
14. Are there dynamic tariffs
15. Popular understanding of electricity tariffs
16. Price signal
17. Proportion of EV fleet

INTERVIEW GUIDELINES TO BRIDGE EXPERTS

INTRODUCTION

1. Short introduction of SENDER, WP3, and more concretely D3.2 objectives

SECTION 1: RENERGETIC PROJECT

1. Short description of the project
2. Demand Response in the RENERgetic project

SECTION 2: NEGAGMENT SRATEGIES

3. Experience in user engagement in the project.
 - Type of target groups and strategies being used
 - Successful rate
 - Barriers and challenges
 - Best practices
4. What kind of communication channels did you use?
5. What do you think are the main motivations that could drive the different groups?
6. What kind of incentives worked best for you?

SECTION 3: ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

7. What do you think is the main popular perception(s) regarding demand response?
8. Do you have experience in collecting data on environmental values or behaviour?
What are best practices in collecting and measuring these data?
9. Have you been involved in research studying social cohesion? What concepts and tools are useful to study this topic?
10. Additional recommendation from your experience

Annex 2: Target user profiles

Target user profiling sheet – ADEE

ENGAGEMENT STRATEGIES

This information will feed D3.2

Target groups (segmented)

Develop/Imagine 3-4 main prototypical profiles that are represented in your pilot area, following the structure:

PROFILE TYPE 1

- a. **Demographic profile** (age range, gender, neighbourhood profile, socioeconomic status, main values [moral/social/environmental]): 35-50 years old couple with kids, living in an owned semi-detached house with at least a High School Diploma or Vocational training.
- b. **Level of house automation:** From low to medium
- c. **How likely is it that they have an EV?** Unlikely
- d. **Knowledge of their electricity tariffs:** Medium understanding of the energy periods but no other concepts included in the tariff.
- e. **Do they pursue strategies to minimize energy expenditure?** Yes
- f. **Main perception/narratives of the SENDER Box demand response technology:** As a way to minimize the energy consumption and automatize their home.
- g. **Main motivations to engage over the long-term with the SENDER Box:** To save money in their electricity bill and feel part of an innovation project.

PROFILE TYPE 2

- a. **Demographic profile (age range, gender, neighbourhood profile, socioeconomic status, main values):** 60-70 years old couple living in a semi-detached house with at least vocational training.
- b. **Level of house automation:** Low
- c. **How likely is it that they have an EV?** Very unlikely
- d. **Knowledge of their electricity tariffs:** Medium
- e. **Do they pursue strategies to minimize energy expenditure?** Yes
- f. **Main perception/narratives of the SENDER Box demand response technology:** As a way to participate in stopping climate change and encourage the clean energies use.
- g. **Main motivations to engage over the long-term with the SENDER Box:** To automatize their home appliances and the feeling that they are doing something to stop the climate change.

PROFILE TYPE 3

- a. **Demographic profile (age range, gender, neighbourhood profile, socioeconomic status, main values [moral/social/environmental]):** Pensioner living alone in a semidetached house
- b. **Level of house automation:** Low level
- c. **How likely is it that they have an EV?** Very unlikely
- d. **Knowledge of their electricity tariffs:** Poor Knowledge
- e. **Do they pursue strategies to minimize energy expenditure?** No

- f. **Main perception/narratives of the SENDER Box demand response technology:** Something to save money in their electricity bills.
- g. **Main motivations to engage over the long-term with the SENDER Box:** Very difficult to find motivation to engage this profile type long-term

PROFILE TYPE 4

- a. **Demographic profile (age range, gender, neighbourhood profile, socioeconomic status, main values [moral/social/environmental]):** 30–40-year-old Person environmentally conscious with active involvement in Energy efficiency; High education; Medium – high standard of living
- b. **Level of house automation:** Medium to high level
- c. **How likely is it that they have an EV?** Likely
- d. **Knowledge of their electricity tariffs:** Strong Knowledge
- e. **Do they pursue strategies to minimize energy expenditure?** Yes
- f. **Main perception/narratives of the SENDER Box demand response technology:** As a method to interact within the community in energy consumption field.
- g. **Main motivations to engage over the long-term with the SENDER Box:** Collaborate in an innovation project to be more Energy efficient, and to promote the use of clean energies.

Key messages per target group – detailed description of the key messages

For each of the profiles described above, detail the key messages you would convey to them to engage them in using the SENDER Box

PROFILE 1: To use state of the art technology in Energy efficiency.

PROFILE 2: To learn to minimize electricity bill and stop the climate change.

PROFILE 3: To save money in electricity bill.

PROFILE 4: To collaborate in a future change of the energy system.

Communication channels used for each target

Detail which communication channels can be used for each of the profiles described above

PROFILE 1: email, workshops

PROFILE 2: email, workshops, phone calls (if they agree to give us their number), Facebook.

PROFILE 3: Through the senior's citizen social club.

PROFILE 4: Through email, workshops, social media.

Stakeholders/Multipliers:

- **Key stakeholders that can help accessing/reaching the targets:**
Local elderly association
Local newspaper, social networks
- **Associations and events that can be used for dissemination of the SENDER services:**
Workshops, Local elderly association

Key activities to perform to reach and engage target groups

- **Key aspects to consider in order to keep the target groups engaged along the project:** Regular communication, dedicated workshops, time-plan fulfilment, performance monitoring.

- **Schedule of the key activities, and communication actions for the engagement of target groups:**
 - a. RECRUITMENT: OCT 2020 – JUN 2022
 - Approaching e-Mails to our cooperative members to raise awareness of the project.
 - Online Workshop to our cooperative members interested in the project.
 - Advertisement in social media.
 - Advertisement in local newspapers and associations.
 - Joint dissemination actions with other H2020 Projects
 - b. PROCUREMENT OF HARDWARE INFRASTRUCTURE AND DEPLOYMENT IN PILOT SITES:
OCT2022-APRIL 2023
 - Privacy Policy meetings with consumers.
 - Specific meetings about the functioning of the system.
 - c. DEMONSTRATION IN PILOT SITES STARTS: APRIL 2023
 - Follow up.

Target user profiling sheet – VTT

ENGAGEMENT STRATEGIES

This information will feed D3.2

Target groups (segmented)

Develop/Imagine 3-4 main prototypical profiles that are represented in your pilot area, following the structure:

PROFILE TYPE 1 – Engineer

- a. **Demographic profile:** age range 30+, gender M, neighbourhood profile, socioeconomic status, main values [moral/social/environmental/practicality/cost efficiency]
- b. **Level of house automation:** Advanced
- c. **How likely is it that they have an EV?** 50 % odds
- d. **Knowledge of their electricity tariffs:** Excellent
- e. **Do they pursue strategies to minimize energy expenditure?** Yes
- f. **Main perception/narratives of the SENDER Box demand response technology:** Interested
- g. **Main motivations to engage over the long-term with the SENDER Box:** Gets data and new insight from technology and regulation point of view

PROFILE TYPE 2 – Environmentally oriented

- a. **Demographic profile:** age range 30+, gender F, neighbourhood profile, socioeconomic status, main values [moral/social/environmental]
- b. **Level of house automation:** Non-existing
- c. **How likely is it that they have an EV?** 10% odds
- d. **Knowledge of their electricity tariffs:** No
- e. **Do they pursue strategies to minimize energy expenditure?** No
- f. **Main perception/narratives of the SENDER Box demand response technology:** Helps the environment and society
- g. **Main motivations to engage over the long-term with the SENDER Box:** Willing to help and make positive impact

PROFILE TYPE 3 – Businessman

- a. **Demographic profile:** age range 40+, gender M, neighbourhood profile, socioeconomic status, main values [moral/social/environmental/time]
- b. **Level of house automation:** Something (security service maybe)
- c. **How likely is it that they have an EV?** 60% odds
- d. **Knowledge of their electricity tariffs:** Some
- e. **Do they pursue strategies to minimize energy expenditure?** Maybe
- f. **Main perception/narratives of the SENDER Box demand response technology:** Services for ease of living, yes please
- g. **Main motivations to engage over the long-term with the SENDER Box:** Ensures that new services will be provided

Key messages per target group – detailed description of the key messages

For each of the profiles described above, detail the key messages you would convey to them to engage them in using the SENDER Box

PROFILE 1: "You will save money"

PROFILE 2: "You will save the earth"

PROFILE 3: "You will save time"

Communication channels used for each target

Detail which communication channels can be used for each of the profiles described above

PROFILE 1 – Forums, Facebook, LinkedIn

PROFILE 2 – Newspapers, Facebook

PROFILE 3 – Direct communication, LinkedIn

Stakeholders/Multipliers:

- **Key stakeholders that can help accessing/reaching the targets**
 - Housing associations, DSOs, Energy Companies
- **Associations and events that can be used for dissemination of the SENDER services:**
 - Seminars about smart living, exhibitions, some events for managers of housing companies (isännöitsijöiden päivät tms.)

Key activities to perform to reach and engage target groups

- **Key aspects to consider in order to keep the target groups engaged along the project:**
 - They should have weekly the possibility to reach to us.
- **Schedule of the key activities, and communication actions for the engagement of target groups**
 - Plans ready before summer 2022, recruitment starts after summer holidays

Target user profiling sheet – WEIZ

ENGAGEMENT STRATEGIES

This information will feed D3.2

Target groups (segmented)

Develop/Imagine 3-4 main prototypical profiles that are represented in your pilot area, following the structure:

PROFILE TYPE 1

- a. **Demographic profile** (age range, gender, neighbourhood profile, socioeconomic status, main values [moral/social/environmental])
Male, Late 40s, Father, two children (14&18) both in school, has a 9-5 Job, well paid, Wife is working too, good Income. Lives in a House, in a good Neighbourhood where all live in houses.
It is important for him to have a well-paid job, acts environmentally friendly to impress others. He has a PV on the roof.
- b. **Level of house automation:** Medium, has all the cool gadgets like Alexa or a robot vacuum cleaner.
- c. **How likely is it that they have an EV?** Yes, a Tesla as a second car
- d. **Knowledge of their electricity tariffs:** He just checks how much he had to pay for the last month. Considering the Energy production of the PV.
- e. **Do they pursue strategies to minimize energy expenditure?** He would like to do so, but he is too lazy to execute it.
- f. **Main perception/narratives of the SENDER Box demand response technology**
- g. **Main motivations to engage over the long-term with the SENDER Box:** Wants to participate, because it is an international Project. Just the fact that it is an innovative project, it motivates him to engage and participate. Maybe to impress others by telling them that he is participating.

PROFILE TYPE 2

- a. **Demographic profile** (age range, gender, neighbourhood profile, socioeconomic status, main values [moral/social/environmental])
Male, 28-35 years old. Young family, 1 Kid, Vegan, Lives in an apartment, building is a bit older, Wife is at home with the children. Must feed the whole family,
Family is the most important thing. Tries to act in environmentally friendly ways, like riding the bike instead of using the car. Always keeping in mind his finances.
- b. **Level of house automation:** Low. Does not have the budget to invest.
- c. **How likely is it that they have an EV?** Unlikely, uses the e-car sharing service in Weiz.
- d. **Knowledge of their electricity tariffs:** Yes. Constantly checking the bill.
- e. **Do they pursue strategies to minimize energy expenditure?** Yes. Tries to save money by reducing the energy (electricity) consumption.
- f. **Main perception/narratives of the SENDER Box demand response technology**

- g. **Main motivations to engage over the long-term with the SENDER Box:** He can evaluate his energy consumption. The SENDER Solution helps him, to find ways to be more effective in consumption.

PROFILE TYPE 3

- a. **Demographic profile** (age range, gender, neighborhood profile, socioeconomic status, main values [moral/social/environmental])
Female, Tech-savvy, 30-35 years old, lives alone in a house, her career is her biggest priority in life, ambitious, independent. She does not intentionally pollute the environment, but in her everyday life she does not really take into consideration when she wants to have or do something.
- b. **Level of house automation:** High, likes to play with home automation gear
- c. **How likely is it that they have an EV?** Likely
- d. **Knowledge of their electricity tariffs:** Yes
- e. **Do they pursue strategies to minimize energy expenditure?** Yes. Just to test her gear and systems, she installed. “Are they working? What can I improve?”
- f. **Main perception/narratives of the SENDER Box demand response technology**
- g. **Main motivations to engage over the long-term with the SENDER Box:** State-of-the art technology. Developed by experts. Try it out! Gear for free!

Key messages per target group – detailed description of the key messages

For each of the profiles described above, detail the key messages you would convey to them to engage them in using the SENDER Box

PROFILE 1: SENDER is a new innovative European project. Be part of it!

PROFILE 2: SENDER identifies the appliances with the most energy consumption. Makes the energy use more efficient. Helps you to save money.

PROFILE 3: New technology, State-of-the-art, Be part of the project (Co-Creation)

Communication channels used for each target

Detail which communication channels can be used for each of the profiles described above

PROFILE 1: Facebook, Regional Newspapers, Events

PROFILE 2: Posters, Events, Generally Print Media

PROFILE 3: LinkedIn, Online-Newspaper,

Stakeholders/Multipliers:

- **Key stakeholders that can help accessing/reaching the targets**
- **Associations and events that can be used for dissemination of the SENDER services:**
Advertisements in trade journals, Trade fair appearances (House Building Fairs, Innovation Fairs, ...)

Key activities to perform to reach and engage target groups

- **Key aspects to consider in order to keep the target groups engaged along the project:**
Weekly or monthly Newsletter, regular Post on Social Media, a Channel where Participants can contact us or even contact other Participants (Forum, Facebook Group, WhatsApp or

Telegram Group Chat, ...), Everyday Support Service in case something is not working (Its not good when the heating system is not working), regular Webinars or Trainings where participants can give new inputs, ...

- **Schedule of the key activities, and communication actions for the engagement of target groups**

Annex 3: Survey to end-users in the demonstration sites

Survey guidelines – ADEE (Catalan)

ENQUESTA DEL SENDER: PROGRAMA EUROPEU D'EFICIÈNCIA ENERGÈTICA

Arreu d'Europa, amb la transició energètica es desenvolupen sistemes d'energia sostenible a nivell social i ambiental de manera que no només la tecnologia és més respectuosa amb el medi ambient, sinó que també ho és amb les necessitats de les persones que les utilitzen. El programa SENDER ofereix a consumidors elèctrics la possibilitat d'involucrar-se en solucions de resposta a la demanda elèctrica i de provar la seva implementació a tres regions pilot a Finlàndia, Àustria i Espanya.

L'objectiu d'aquesta enquesta és recollir i conèixer les necessitats, interessos i preferències dels ciutadans de la regió pilot d'Alginet per tal d'adaptar la implementació del programa a aquestes i així assegurar que el programa és útil per a la comunitat, i que les persones interessades en participar-hi ho poden fer.

1. DADES PERSONALS DEMOGRÀFIQUES

Per l'objectiu d'aquest estudi, necessitem algunes dades bàsiques sobre tu.

Edat	<input type="checkbox"/> 18 - 24	<input type="checkbox"/> 25 - 34	<input type="checkbox"/> 35 - 50	<input type="checkbox"/> 51 - 64	<input type="checkbox"/> > 65
Gènere	<input type="checkbox"/> Masculí	<input type="checkbox"/> Femení	<input type="checkbox"/> Altre		
Nivell d'escolarització:					
<input type="checkbox"/> Escolarització Obligatòria					
<input type="checkbox"/> Batxillerat					
<input type="checkbox"/> Escola Tècnica / Formació Professional					
<input type="checkbox"/> Grau Universitari					
<input type="checkbox"/> Màster / Doctorat					
<input type="checkbox"/> Altre					
Ingressos mensuals nets (personals):					
<input type="checkbox"/> < 1.000€		<input type="checkbox"/> 1.000€ - 1.999€		<input type="checkbox"/> 2.000 – 2.999€	
<input type="checkbox"/> > 3.000€					
Marca l'opció que més s'adequa a la teva situació d'habitatge:					

	Habitatge unifamiliar	Conjunt/Bloc d'habitatge de múltiples famílies
Habitatge de propietat pròpia		
Habitatge de lloguer		
Model de llar: <input type="checkbox"/> Parella amb nen(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Parella <input type="checkbox"/> Casa unipersonal <input type="checkbox"/> Llar compartida entre múltiples adults		
Indica el nivell d'automatització domèstica que tens a casa: <input type="checkbox"/> Sense automatització <input type="checkbox"/> Automatització baixa (il·luminació) <input type="checkbox"/> Automatització mitja (temperatura interior automatitzada) <input type="checkbox"/> Automatització alta (temperatura interior automatitzada i altres [carregador de vehicle elèctric, planificació, il·luminació, seguretat...]).		

2. CONEIXEMENT I INTERESSOS

Aquesta secció del qüestionari adreça el teu coneixement i interès en el canvi climàtic, el sector energètic i els mecanismes de resposta a la demanda elèctrica. Per resposta a la demanda s'entén el fet d'adaptar el nostre consum elèctric segons la disponibilitat i el preu de l'energia a la xarxa elèctrica.

Indica el grau en el què estàs d'acord amb les afirmacions següents:					
	1 = Totalment en desacord	2	3	4	5= Totalment d'acord
Sento una obligació moral de fer la meua aportació a frenar el canvi climàtic					

L'evidència científica del canvi climàtic no és prou fiable					
Els governs haurien de fer reduir o canviar el consum energètic de la gent si així es mitiga el canvi climàtic					
Considero irrellevant per a mi la informació sobre energia sostenible					
No em sento atret(a) per les noves tecnologies					

Has sentit a parlar de mecanismes de Resposta a la Demanda / Flexibilitat Elèctrica?

Sí No N/A

Estàs d'acord amb l'afirmació "Considero que tinc suficient informació per a avaluar de manera adequada si em podria beneficiar d'aquestes tecnologies (de resposta la demanda elèctrica)"?

Totalment en desacord Parcialment en desacord

Bastant d'acord Totalment d'acord

Coneixes programes de la Unió Europea per afrontar el canvi climàtic i la crisi energètica?

No Sí, n'he sentit/llegit alguna cosa. Sí, els conec una mica i hi participo/he participat activament N/A

Segons la teva percepció, avalua amb valors de 1 = "Baix" a 5= "Alt" aquests programes en relació a si compleixen amb els criteris següents:

	1 = Baix	2	3	4	5 = Alt	N/A
Utilitat						
Fiabilitat						
Èxit						

3. NECESSITATS DELS CIUTADANS PER A L'AVANÇ DE L'EFICIÈNCIA ENERGÈTICA

Aquesta secció demana la teva opinió sobre prioritats ambientals de la societat, i sobre què poden fer els ciutadans en el seu consum energètic per contribuir a la sostenibilitat. També pregunta què necessiten els consumidors energètics per a començar a utilitzar més tecnologies energèticament eficients, si hi estan interessats.

Si necessitessis un nou electrodomèstic, fins a quin punt cadascun dels següents criteris guiaria la teva tria?						
	1 = Gens	2	3	4	5 = Molt	N /A
Preu						
Baix consum energètic						
Llarg cicle de vida de producte						
Garantia de reparació						
Valor estètic						
Programació intel·ligent/automatitzada						

Coneixes el concepte d'Eficiència Energètica?						
<input type="checkbox"/> Sí <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A						
T'interessa augmentar l'eficiència energètica de casa teva?						
<input type="checkbox"/> Sí <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A						
En quina mesura les següents raons et motivarien a adoptar mesures d'eficiència energètica a casa?						
	1 = Gens	2	3	4	5 = Molt	N/A
Inversió econòmica mínima						
Estalvis en energia (€)						
No requereix temps o dedicació						
Mesures fàcils d'implementar						

Augmentar el coneixement que tinc del meu consum energètic						
Frenar el canvi climàtic						
Reconeixement social						
<p>Què et caldria per a involucrar-te a llarg termini en programes a Alginet que abordin reptes socials i ambientals?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Comunicació freqüent <input type="checkbox"/> Esdeveniments socials i formar part d'una comunitat de participants <input type="checkbox"/> Seminaris i adquirir coneixements nous <input type="checkbox"/> Beneficis socials addicionals (e.g. descomptes en comerç local, visites culturals) <input type="checkbox"/> Assessorament per a adoptar més mesures de sostenibilitat <input type="checkbox"/> Altres (si et plau, especifica) 						

4. OPINIÓ I PARTICIPACIÓ

Aquesta secció et pregunta pel teu interès personal en el programa, i suggeriments o valoracions que tinguis al respecte.

Tens algun suggeriment o comentari que t'agradaria compartir (aspectes a millorar, temes no abordats per l'enquesta...)?

T'agradaria ser contactat per a participar en el programa SENDER?

Sí No

En cas afirmatiu, especifica la teva adreça electrònica:

PROTECCIÓ DE DADES: D'acord amb les normatives vigents en protecció de dades personals, el Reglament (UE) 2016/679 de 27 d'abril de 2016 (GDPR) i la Llei Orgànica (ES) 3/2018 de 5 de desembre (LOPDGDD), us informem que les dades personals i adreça de correu electrònic recaptat, seran tractats sota la responsabilitat de l'associació ECOSERVEIS, soci del projecte SENDER, per a la gestió de la vostra participació en l'estudi socioeconòmic sobre la població pel disseny de l'entregable "D3.2 Consumer Engagement Strategies Guidelines" i es conservaran MENTRE SIGUIN NECESSÀRIES PER A DUR A TERME AQUESTS OBJECTIUS.

Gràcies per dedicar el teu temps a completar l'enquesta!

Survey guidelines – VTT (English)

SENDER: EUROPEAN PROGRAMME FOR ENERGY EFFICIENCY

Throughout Europe, the energy transition gives a growing place to sustainable energies meaning that not only technologies are more and more environmentally friendly but also that they aim to be adapted to their consumers. The SENDER programme aims to engage end-users into demand response solutions and test the implementation of these solutions in three pilot regions, in Finland, Austria, and Spain.

The purpose of this survey is to have a better understanding of the needs, interests, and preferences of the citizens of your pilot region in order to adapt the programme to ensure that it is useful for your community, and that people interested in participating face no obstacles to do so.

1. PERSONAL DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

For the purpose of this study, we need some basic information about you.

Age	<input type="checkbox"/> 18 - 24	<input type="checkbox"/> 25 - 34	<input type="checkbox"/> 35 - 50	<input type="checkbox"/> 51 - 64	<input type="checkbox"/> > 65
Gender	<input type="checkbox"/> Male	<input type="checkbox"/> Female	<input type="checkbox"/> Other		
Education level:					
<input type="checkbox"/> Less than high school					
<input type="checkbox"/> High school graduate					
<input type="checkbox"/> Vocational / Trade / Technical School					
<input type="checkbox"/> Bachelor's degree					
<input type="checkbox"/> Masters / Doctorate /PhD					
<input type="checkbox"/> Other					
Net monthly income:					
<input type="checkbox"/> < 1.000€		<input type="checkbox"/> 1.000€ - 2.500€		<input type="checkbox"/> 2.500 – 4.000€	
<input type="checkbox"/> > 4.000€					
Postal Code:					
Please tick the box that best describes your tenure arrangement:					
	Single-family house		Multi-household building		
Own					

Rent		
Household Type: <input type="checkbox"/> Couple with child(ren) <input type="checkbox"/> Couple <input type="checkbox"/> One person household <input type="checkbox"/> Multiple adults in cohabitation <input type="checkbox"/> Single-parent household		
Please indicate the level of home automation you have at home. <input type="checkbox"/> No automation <input type="checkbox"/> Low automation (adjustable indoor radiators) <input type="checkbox"/> Medium automation (centralised automated indoor temperature) <input type="checkbox"/> High automation (centralised automated indoor temperature and others (electric vehicle charger, scheduling, lightning, security...))		
Do you own an electric vehicle? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Do you have photovoltaic panels at home? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
Do you plan on acquiring an electric vehicle and/or photovoltaic panels in the next five years? <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes: an electric vehicle <input type="checkbox"/> Yes: photovoltaic panels <input type="checkbox"/> Yes: both <input type="checkbox"/> I already have both		

2. MOTIVATIONS AND INTERESTS

This section of the questionnaire focuses on your present knowledge and interest in demand response mechanisms and the energy sector. Demand response refers to adapting our energy consumption according to the availability of the electric grid, and to get some financial compensation in exchange for this service that is provided to the grid.

Please, indicate how much you agree with the following statements.

	1 = Totally disagree	2	3	4	5 = Totally agree
I feel a moral obligation to do my bit on climate change.					
Evidence of climate change is not reliable.					
Governments should make people reduce or change their energy consumption if it mitigates climate change.					
I consider information on sustainable energy to be irrelevant to me.					
I do not feel attracted to new technologies					

<p>Have you ever heard about Demand Response / Flexibility mechanisms?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A</p>
<p>Do you agree with the affirmation? "I feel that I have enough information to assess adequately whether I could benefit from these technologies".</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Totally disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Somehow disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Partially agree <input type="checkbox"/> Totally agree</p>

Are you aware about the existence of EU programmes to tackle climate change and the energy crisis?

- No
- Yes, I have heard something
- Yes, I have heard something, and actively participate or have participated
- N/A

Please indicate a range from 1 = “Low” to 5 = “High”, according to your perception about these programmes for the different characteristics below.

	1 = Low	2	3	4	5 = High	N/A
Usefulness						
Trustworthy						
Successfulness						

3. NEEDS OF CITIZENS IN THE PURSUIT OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY

This section is focused on your opinion regarding society’s environmental priorities, and what could citizens do in their energy usage to contribute to efficiency and sustainability. It also asks about what citizens need to switch to energy-efficient technologies if they wish to do so.

If you were to acquire a new household electrical appliance (kodinkoneet), how much would each of the following criteria guide your choice?

	1 = Not at all	2	3	4	5 = Very much	N/A
Price						
Low energy consumption						
Product durability						
Reliable repair warranty						
Aesthetic value						
Automatic/smart programming						

Are you aware about the concept of Energy Efficiency?

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A						
Would you be interested in being more energetically efficient at home?						
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A						
Which will your motivation be to implement energy efficiency measures at home? Being 1 = “Low motivation” and 5 = “High motivation”.						
	1 = Low	2	3	4	5 = High	N/A
Low investment						
Energy savings (€)						
Not time-consuming						
Easy to apply measures						
Improving my knowledge about my energy consumption						
Alleviating climate change and reducing pollution						
Social recognition						
What would you need for your long-term commitment in programmes tackling social and environmental challenges in your town/city?						
<input type="checkbox"/> Frequent communication and responsiveness <input type="checkbox"/> Social events and being part of a community <input type="checkbox"/> Workshops and acquiring new knowledge <input type="checkbox"/> Additional social benefits (e.g. discounts in local commerce, cultural visits) <input type="checkbox"/> Guidance to adopt further measures to go beyond the initial programme <input type="checkbox"/> Capacity to track the impact of my personal/household actions <input type="checkbox"/> Others (please, specify)						

4. OPINION AND PARTICIPATION

This section interrogates your personal interest in the purpose of the project, and on suggestions and assessment that you may have.

Do you have any suggestion or comment that you would like to share (aspects that could be improved, topics unaddressed by the survey...)?

Would you like to be contacted to participate in the SENDER programme?

Yes No

If yes, specify email address:

DATA PROTECTION: In accordance with current regulations on personal data protection, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of 27 April 2016 (GDPR), we inform you that the personal data and e-mail address collected, will be treated under the responsibility of ECOSERVEIS, project partner to the SENDER project, for the management of your participation in the socioeconomic study of the population for the design of "D3.2 Consumer Engagement Strategies Guidelines" and will be preserved AS LONG AS NECESSARY TO CARRY OUT THESE OBJECTIVES.

Accept

Thank you for taking the time to complete the questionnaire!

Survey guidelines – WEIZ (German)

SENDER: EUROPÄISCHES PROJEKT FÜR ENERGIEEFFIZIENZ

In ganz Europa wird im Rahmen der Energiewende nachhaltigen Energien ein immer größerer Stellenwert eingeräumt. Aber es sollen nicht nur die Technologien immer umweltfreundlicher werden, sondern auch Nutzer: innen mehr eingebunden werden. Das SENDER-Projekt zielt darauf ab, Nutzer:innen in Lösungen zur Nachfragesteuerung einzubinden und die Umsetzung dieser Lösungen in drei Pilotregionen in Finnland, Österreich und Spanien zu testen.

Der Zweck dieser Umfrage ist es, die Bedürfnisse, Interessen und Vorlieben der Bürger:innen in den Pilotregionen besser zu verstehen, um das Projekt so anzupassen, dass es für Ihre Gemeinschaft nützlich ist.

1. DEMOGRAPHISCHE DATEN

In diesem Abschnitt der Umfrage benötigen wir einige demographische Daten.

Alter 18 - 24 25 - 34 35 - 50 51 - 64 > 65

Geschlecht <input type="checkbox"/> Männlich <input type="checkbox"/> Weiblich <input type="checkbox"/> Divers		
Höchste abgeschlossene Ausbildung: <input type="checkbox"/> Unterstufe <input type="checkbox"/> Oberstufe <input type="checkbox"/> Lehrabschlussprüfung <input type="checkbox"/> Matura, Berufsreifeprüfung <input type="checkbox"/> Bachelorabschluss <input type="checkbox"/> Master-, Doktorabschluss <input type="checkbox"/> Sonstiges:		
Monatliches Nettoeinkommen: <input type="checkbox"/> < 1.000 € <input type="checkbox"/> 1.000 – 1.999 € <input type="checkbox"/> 2.000 – 2.999€ <input type="checkbox"/> > 3.000 €		
Bitte kreuzen Sie das Kästchen an, das Ihr Wohnverhältnis am besten beschreibt:		
	Einfamilienhaus	Gebäude mit mehreren Haushalten (Wohnung)
Besitz		
Miete		
Haushaltsform: <input type="checkbox"/> Einpersonenhaushalt <input type="checkbox"/> Mehrpersonenhaushalt <input type="checkbox"/> Mehrpersonenhaushalt mit Kind(ern)		
Home-Automatation: <input type="checkbox"/> Ich will keine Automatisierung <input type="checkbox"/> Ich habe kein Home-Automation-System, würde aber gerne einige Geräte automatisieren <input type="checkbox"/> Ich habe Home-Automation, würde es aber gerne steigern <input type="checkbox"/> Mein Zuhause ist vollautomatisiert		
Haben Sie ein Elektrofahrzeug?		

<input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein
Haben Sie zu Hause eine Photovoltaikanlage?
<input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein

2. KENNTNISSE UND INTERESSEN

In diesem Abschnitt der Umfrage geht es um Ihre derzeitigen Kenntnisse und Ihr Interesse an Demand-Response-Mechanismen und dem Energiesektor. Unter Demand Response versteht man die Anpassung unseres Energieverbrauchs an die Verfügbarkeit des Stromnetzes.

Bitte geben Sie an, wie sehr Sie den folgenden Aussagen zustimmen.					
	1 = Völlig anderer Meinung	2	3	4	5= Völlig einverstan den
Ich fühle mich moralisch verpflichtet, meinen Beitrag zum Klimawandel zu leisten.					
Die Beweise für den Klimawandel sind nicht zuverlässig.					
Die Regierungen sollten die Menschen dazu bringen, ihren Energieverbrauch zu reduzieren oder zu ändern, wenn dies den Klimawandel eindämmt.					
Informationen über nachhaltige Energie interessieren mich nicht.					
Neue Technologien interessieren mich nicht.					

<p>Haben Sie schon einmal von Demand Response / Flexibilitätsmechanismen gehört?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> N/A</p>
<p>Stimmen Sie dieser Aussage zu? "Ich habe das Gefühl, dass ich über genügend Informationen verfüge, um beurteilen zu können, ob ich von diesen Technologien profitieren könnte."</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Stimmt gar nicht <input type="checkbox"/> Stimmt eher nicht <input type="checkbox"/> Stimmt zum Teil <input type="checkbox"/> Stimmt völlig</p>

<p>Sind Ihnen EU-Projekte (Programme) zur Bewältigung der Klima- und Energiekrise bekannt?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Nein</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Ja, Ich habe von einigen gehört</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Ja, ich habe bereits an einem Projekt (mehreren Projekten) teilgenommen oder nehme gerade teil</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> N/A</p>

<p>Wenn „Ja“: Bitte bewerten Sie die Ihnen bekannten Projekte (Programme) in Bezug auf die nachstehenden Merkmale auf einer Skala von 1 = "gering" bis 5 = "hoch".</p>						
	1 = Gering	2	3	4	5 = Hoch	N/A
Nutzen						
Zuverlässigkeit						
Erfolg						

3. BEDÜRFNISSE DER BÜRGER BEIM STREBEN NACH ENERGIEEFFIZIENZ

In diesem Abschnitt der Umfrage geht es um Ihre Meinung zu den Prioritäten der Gesellschaft zum Thema Umweltschutz und was die Bürger in ihrer Energienutzung tun könnten, um zur Effizienz und Nachhaltigkeit beizutragen.

Wenn Sie ein neues elektrisches Haushaltsgerät kaufen würden, inwieweit würden Sie sich bei Ihrer Wahl von den folgenden Kriterien leiten lassen?						
	1 = Gar nicht	2	3	4	5 = Sehr	N/A
Preis						
Geringer Energieverbrauch						
Haltbarkeit						
Verlässliche Reparaturgarantie						
Ästhetischer Wert						
Automatische/intelligente Programmierung						

Sind Sie mit dem Konzept „Energieeffizienz“ vertraut?						
<input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> N/A						
Sind Sie daran interessiert, Ihr Zuhause energieeffizienter zu gestalten?						
<input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> N/A						
Wie sehr würde Sie die folgenden Gründe dazu motivieren, Energieeffizienzmaßnahmen zu Hause durchzuführen? Dabei ist 1 = "niedrige Motivation" und 5 = "hohe Motivation".						
	1 = Niedrig	2	3	4	5 = Hoch	N/A
Geringe Investitionskosten						
Energieeinsparung (€)						
Nicht zeitaufwendig						
Einfach anzuwendende Maßnahmen						
Verbesserung meines Wissens über meinen Energieverbrauch						
Abschwächung des Klimawandels und Reduzierung der Umweltverschmutzung						

Gesellschaftliche Anerkennung						
<p>Was würden Sie für ein langfristiges Engagement in Projekten zur Bewältigung sozialer und ökologischer Herausforderungen in Ihrer Stadt benötigen?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Regelmäßige Kommunikation seitens der Projektpartner</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Veranstaltungen und Zugehörigkeit zu einer Gemeinschaft</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Workshops und Seminare</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Zusätzliche soziale Leistungen (z. B. Ermäßigungen im örtlichen Handel, ...)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Unterstützung bei der Durchführung weiterer Maßnahmen, die über das Projekt hinausgehen</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Sonstiges:</p>						

4. Meinung und Teilnahme

In diesem Abschnitt der Umfrage werden Sie nach Vorschlägen und Einschätzungen gefragt, die Sie möglicherweise zum Projekt haben.

<p>Haben Sie Vorschläge oder Anmerkungen, die Sie uns mitteilen möchten (Verbesserungen; Themen, die in der Umfrage nicht angesprochen wurden, ...)?</p>
<p>Möchten Sie kontaktiert werden, um am Projekt SENDER teilzunehmen?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein</p> <p>Wenn ja, geben Sie bitte Ihre E-Mail-Adresse an:</p>

DATENSCHUTZ: In Übereinstimmung mit den geltenden Vorschriften zum Schutz personenbezogener Daten, Verordnung (EU) 2016/679 vom 27. April 2016 (GDPR), informieren wir Sie darüber, dass die gesammelten personenbezogenen Daten und die E-Mail-Adresse unter der Verantwortung von ECOSERVEIS, Projektpartner des SENDER-Projekts, stehen. Die Daten werden für die Verwaltung Ihrer Teilnahme an der sozioökonomischen Studie der Bevölkerung für die Gestaltung des Projektziels "D3.2 Consumer Engagement Strategies Guidelines" bearbeitet und so lange aufbewahrt, wie es für die Erreichung dieser Ziele notwendig ist. Ihre Daten werden nicht an dritte (nicht am Projekt beteiligte) Parteien weitergegeben.

Zustimmung

Vielen Dank, dass Sie sich die Zeit genommen haben, an der Umfrage teilzunehmen!

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